

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF DEVELOPMENT COMMUNICATION

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**COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES OF
WOMEN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY LEADERS:
AN ETHNOMETHODOLOGICAL STUDY OF PODCAST NARRATIVES**

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14 September 2024

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This paper prepared by **LEE TROY BERNAL CALIMLIM** with the title: **“COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES OF WOMEN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY LEADERS: AN ETHNOMETHODOLOGICAL STUDY OF PODCAST NARRATIVES”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Program.

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Biographical Sketch

Lee Troy Bernal Calimlim is a communication professional with a diverse portfolio spanning media, corporate communications, and youth advocacy. A graduate of New Era University College of Communication, Troy's early years were marked by experience in stage productions, where he led and co-directed theater productions.

Throughout his academic journey, Troy distinguished himself through leadership and academic excellence, being recognized as Leadership Awardee from the NSTP Department, President's Lister, and for several Achievements in Journalism, Development Communication, and Corporate Communication. His work as a writer and director for NEU's campus magazine television show, "AveNEU," contributed to the program's success, earning back-to-back Anak TV Awards in 2017 and 2018.

After graduation, Troy joined a faith-based non-profit media as a writer, where he played a key role in adapting existing shows and content for virtual platforms and setup during the pandemic. His career then expanded into technical and content writing, where he contributed to projects for organizations like SEAMEO INNOTECH and UNICEF. Later, he transitioned to the FinTech industry, where he redefined brand messaging and initiated key partnerships for a transport company.

Currently, Troy manages corporate communication at Asticom Technology Inc., the shared service arm of Globe Telecom. His work has led to numerous awards, and he has implemented innovative tech like Meltwater for media monitoring. His contributions were recognized when he was nominated for the STRIVE Awards 2023, the annual employee recognition program of the organization.

Beyond his professional achievements, Troy is an active participant in youth leadership initiatives across Southeast Asia. He has represented the Philippines at events like the ASEAN Youth Conference in Jakarta, Indonesia, Asia Youth Summit in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, and the Universal Youth Leaders Summit in Bangkok, Thailand, where he has been instrumental in shaping discussions on youth employment and sustainable development policies and recommendations.

Troy is currently pursuing a Master's degree in Development Communication at the University of the Philippines Open University, furthering his commitment to leveraging communication for development and positive impact.

Acknowledgement

“For I know the plans I have for you,” declares the Lord, “plans to prosper you and not to harm you, plans to give you hope and a future.”

- Jeremiah 29:11

I never would have made it this far, ran and finish this course, without the grace, guidance, and support of so many.

First and foremost, to the Lord God, Our Almighty Father—no words can express the depth of my gratitude for the blessings you have given me. You truly do put all things in order for the good of your people. All honor, glory, and praises belong to You.

To my Thesis Adviser, Dr. Jean A. Saludadez, your guidance has been pivotal in helping me complete my MDC journey. Thank you for accepting me as your advisee, even though I wasn't your student before. Your constant support, timely nudges, and motivation kept me going, even when I felt like giving up.

To my Thesis Committee Members, Dr. Benjamina Paula G. Flor and Dr. Grace J. Alfonso, both of whom I was fortunate to learn from during my time in MDC. Your insights and teachings have been invaluable, and I am so grateful for the opportunity to grow through your guidance.

To my family—May, Meg, and Mitz—thank you for always standing by me in my every decision and pursuit. I hope I've made you proud.

To my friends, my support system—you've been with me through it all: the late-night study sessions, the frustrations, and the moments of doubt. Thank you for lending an ear, a shoulder, and your time.

To my mentor, Monalice G. Aguilar, your inspiration dates back to my undergraduate days and continues to guide me even now. Thank you for being a constant source of encouragement.

To my organization, for supporting my academic endeavors, and to my colleagues and leaders who cheered me on and embraced my pursuits.

To the administration, thank you for giving your blessing and allowing me to embark on this journey. Your guidance and care have been felt every step of the way.

Semper Gratus

(Always Grateful)

Dedication

Dedicated to my late grandmother, Aurea Bernal—

the very embodiment of strength, determination, and resilience.

She weathered every storm life threw her way and raised me into the man I am today.

And to all the women in my life—my mom, my sisters, my mentors and leaders—

thank you for inspiring me every day.

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Abstract

The study explored the communicative practices of women information technology (IT) leaders, how their views of the industry shape these practices, and what these practices achieve in their leadership roles. The study was grounded in the Sociocultural Tradition of Communication, as proposed by Craig (1999), where communication is viewed as the (re)production of “shared sociocultural patterns.” Using ethnomethodology as a qualitative research method, the study explored the communicative practices of women leaders through narratives present in podcast conversations from four (4) podcast episodes featuring different women IT leaders. These podcasts were transcribed and then subjected to an ethnomethodological analysis.

The findings identified five key views of these women IT leaders: (1) the industry is continuously changing, evolving, and disruptive; (2) the industry requires flexibility, adaptability, and agility; (3) success is defined by resilience and problem-solving; (4) the industry is diverse and highly collaborative; and (5) customer-centricity and satisfaction are important in the industry.

Similarly, the study described five communicative practices among these women IT leaders, particularly: (1) women leaders practice continuous learning and self-improvement; (2) women leaders practice adaptability and situational leadership; (3) women leaders practice open and transparent communication; (4) women leaders practice empathy and understanding; and (5) women leaders practice data-driven, tech-enhanced, and customer-focused communication.

Finally, the study also identified four accomplishments and leadership outcomes of the women IT leaders’ communicative practices, which includes: (1) keeping the

company stable and sustainable; (2) keeping the company competitive and relevant; (3) improving team collaboration and engagement; and (4) enabling and promoting adaptability and innovation.

Keywords: *women leadership; information technology; communicative practices; ethnomethodology; podcast narratives*

Chapter I

RATIONALE

Women in Leadership Roles

It is without a doubt that the COVID-19 pandemic has affected many if not all, businesses, and the economy worldwide. This also reflects the reality that many businesses saw the need to view leadership differently. One change that this pandemic drove further was the push for diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) practices among businesses. While companies have already included such in their strategies, many more followed suit and further embraced such practices. As Moreno-Gómez et al. (2018) illustrated, diversity in leadership greatly improves organizational performance. This particular research seeks to peruse the nuanced communicative practices employed by women IT leaders, while also exploring how their views inform these practices and what these practices accomplish in their leadership roles.

The rationale of this study is rooted in a broader societal context, with the goal of contributing to Sustainable Development Goal 8: "Decent Work and Economic Growth," focusing on achieving full and productive employment and decent work for all, irrespective of gender (8.5). By exploring the communicative practices of women IT leaders through podcast narratives, this study helps us better understand the interaction between language, gender, and leadership.

Women Leaders in IT

The representation of women in leadership roles, or the lack thereof, remains a longstanding issue in different countries, the Philippines included. In a report from the

Philippine Business Coalition for Women Empowerment and Philippine Women's Economic Network, it was noted that in the Philippines, only 29 percent of C-level positions are occupied by women and that in the technology industry, only 23 percent held leadership positions worldwide (PBCWE & PhilWEN, 2019).

More research should be done on the unique points of view and communicative practices of women IT leaders, especially concerning how they address challenges and opportunities. This study responds to that call, hoping to offer more insights into the way communicative practices are used by women IT leaders, exploring how their views influence these practices and the outcomes they accomplish in leadership.

Women leaders' experiences in a male-dominated society have been explored in numerous situations, showing the obstacles they confront, such as gender prejudice, discrimination, and a lack of support (Paraggua et al., 2022). These difficulties are especially visible in the technology sector, where women face major hurdles to access and progress. Addressing these hurdles, as identified in the study by Hejase et al (2013), involves acknowledging the "factors that may lead to the glass ceiling, discrimination, and bias against women in managerial positions." To better understand this issue, it is crucial to consider the concept of the "glass ceiling," which was first coined by Marilyn Loden in 1978. This term refers to the invisible barrier that prevents certain individuals from advancing to higher managerial or executive positions within organizations or industries (Kagan, 2022).

The study explored the communicative practices that women IT leaders employ, practices that are often overlooked or taken for granted due to women's underrepresentation in leadership roles within the technology sector. This

underrepresentation, together with challenges they encounter such as gender bias and discrimination, makes it important to study the communicative practices these women leaders use to navigate their professional lives and succeed in this male-dominated field.

Use of Ethnomethodology in Podcasts

By using ethnomethodology as both framework and methodology, the study focused on the 'taken-for-granted' aspects of everyday interactions. Ethnomethodology is different from other research approaches because it focuses on analyzing interactions. In fact, conversation analysis is held as the “ethnomethodological study of talk in interaction” (Garcia, 2013). Podcast is used in this study to observe the communicative practices of women IT leaders from the narratives present within the podcast conversations. It is assumed that the communicative practices are embedded in the podcast narratives, and that these narratives reflect their day-to-day interactions.

With that, the epistemological process of this study involved making sense of the women IT leaders' interactions. The narratives present in the conversations captured through podcast are considered as a form of knowledge. It is important to highlight this, as epistemology is “regarded as a core area of philosophy because it deals with the nature of our knowledge” (Sol & Heng, 2022). Furthermore, Sol & Heng also emphasized the indispensable role of the researcher given the subjective nature of this approach.

Podcasts have become a platform where thought leaders interact. Podcasts and conversations found in them can provide a space for leaders to share their experiences, insights, and advice. This makes it a helpful resource to understand the communicative practices of people in leadership positions. The use of podcast in this study served as a

creative and innovative approach as it captures the conversations as they happen, while allowing the researcher to analyze the narratives in-depth. By looking into the podcast conversations of women IT leaders, we can better understand their communicative practices in a format that is both accessible and influential.

Finally, the study hopes to provide perspectives and insights that could inform policies, practices, and interventions that would further empower the impact of women leaders in the field.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The body of knowledge about women's leadership is always expanding as new information is added now and then. With that, this review of the literature will explore the experiences of women IT leaders including their opportunities and challenges; women leadership in the Philippines and their communicative practices; and finally explore podcasts as a medium of communication.

Experiences of Women IT Leaders

In leadership, communication is becoming more and more important, especially for women in the IT sector. With technology changing the way we communicate and work together, women leaders' distinctive ways of communicating have garnered attention. Oppenauer (2021) highlighted such qualities as the often-overlooked impact of communication, empathy, and collaboration skills.

Akbari and Pratomo (2021) emphasized in a study how "technology has altered communication styles in modern organizations, and leaders need to adapt to these changes to be effective". Female leaders embodying the qualities mentioned earlier (communication, empathy, and collaboration) are in more advantageous positions than those who do not possess such skills for these are proven to be useful in virtual and remote work setups.

In an article from Beales (2023), it was noted that "companies with diverse leadership teams are more likely to be innovative and have better financial performance".

The unique perspective of female leaders like the ones identified by Malek & Jaguli (2018) as the belief that society is a collective therefore decisions should be made as a team, results in better decision-making and problem-solving, as reflected in insights from Mariappan (2021) which state that “diverse companies outperform their less diverse peers when it comes to innovation, problem-solving, and increased agility.”

Zooming in on a study about digital transformation among SMEs, Alam et al. (2022) emphasized the gender-specific differences in perceptions, with findings indicating that women-led SMEs exhibit distinct perspectives on digital transformation compared to their male-led counterparts. The study draws attention to the subtle gendered nuances in how people view digital technology and its place in long-term, profitable company growth.

Baroudi's (2022) research on Arab female educational leaders during crises sheds light on effective leadership qualities, such as flexibility, proactiveness, and service orientation, crucial for successful digital transformation. Likewise, Oppenauer (2021) underscored the significance of leveraging the skills of female employees in the tech industry during digital transformation.

Finally, insights on leading teams through transformation and managing digital transformation during a pandemic emphasize the importance of understanding the 'why' behind the change, setting clear goals, and fostering diversity for innovative outcomes (Mariappan, 2021). Collectively, these studies contribute to understanding the multifaceted experiences of women leaders in the dynamic landscape of digital transformation within the IT sector.

Challenges of Women in Leadership

While many benefits can be had by having female leaders driving the change in digital times, many women still face challenges in their leadership journeys. One challenge identified in the study by Alam, et al. (2022) stated that the gender gap and digital divide can “limit the ability of women to participate fully in the digital economy, which in turn can limit their ability to lead in the digital age”. This is most evident in SMEs where women often face a lack of representation in leadership positions, as reflected in a study by Investing in Women & The University of Sydney (2019) which states that only 20% of SMEs have women in major leadership positions.

Similarly, the literature also described that there is a need to develop new competencies in the digital age such as digital literacy, and innovative and strategic thinking (Alam et al., 2022; Baroudi, 2022; Huynh, 2020). Likewise, new ways of working also required new ways of leading. This highlights the need for better collaboration skills, especially when leading virtual and remote teams (Malek & Jaguli, 2018).

Digital skills have become one of the most important factors for women leaders. With the lack of digital skills, female leaders might face difficulties keeping up with the changes brought about by adopting technologies in the digital transformation era. In a study by Fransson and Frisk (2021), it was mentioned how the pandemic further pushed the need for better digital skills and that companies should invest in them for both leaders and employees.

Similarly, Cherneski (2020) highlighted how digital transformation impacts better decision-making, and more effective communication, while Baroudi (2022) emphasized the need for digital and transformational leadership skills in crisis leadership, while Dasig

(2020) emphasized how digital literacy and access improved leadership skills and opportunities for female leaders.

Other than the gender gap and digital divide, female leaders also faced stereotypes and cultural biases. As stated by Hejase, et al. (2013), “Women leaders in Lebanon face many challenges due to cultural and societal norms that place greater emphasis on family responsibilities and child-rearing.” Due to these traditional gender roles, women leaders encountered obstacles to career advancement and must often put in extra effort to demonstrate their dedication to their profession (ibid). This is very much similar to the biases in other countries that often limit women’s leadership opportunities as mentioned in studies by Cherneski (2020) and Moreno-Gómez, et al., (2018).

Women also experienced harassment and gender-based discrimination at work, even when working online. Larsen (2021) revealed how women experienced harassment online in virtual meetings which affected their decision-making and limited their participation. This is similar to what Alam, et al. (2022) and Moreno-Gómez, et al. (2018) mentioned on how technology enabled new forms of discrimination. Such discriminations and biases based on gender also limited the access of female leaders to opportunities, particularly in the technology field (Aldekhyyel, et al., 2021; Appiah, 2020).

Opportunities for Women in Leadership

On a different note, digital transformation has created opportunities for women in leadership. In an article by Mariappan (2021), it was mentioned how technologies provided autonomy and flexibility for women at work. Women leaders can benefit from the use of different platforms and tech at their disposal. Alam, et al. (2022) differentiated

the challenges faced by female and male leaders in adopting digital tech, which is related to the findings of Huynh (2020) which highlighted how digital transformation paved new avenues for women to assert their leadership. Aldekhyyel, et al. (2021), likewise, saw how it improved equality and reduced gender bias.

In the same vein, PBCWE & PhilWEN (2019) noted how having women in leadership positions and corporate boards leads to better financial and business outcomes. Similarly, Moreno-Gómez, et al. (2018) found in their study that firms with more diverse board and management teams tended to perform better than those with homogeneous teams. Organizations can bank on women to lead digital transformation in their companies. With fresh perspectives, women leaders can further the push for digital transformation with great consideration of more ethical and sustainable practices (Alam et al., 2022).

Women's Leadership in the Philippine Context

The literature on women's leadership in the Philippines offers a comprehensive understanding of the cultural foundations that allow Filipina leaders to be effective and to resonate in their roles, as well as their leadership and communicative practices.

Firstly, Filipina leaders in education promote fairness, equality, and cooperative decision-making, with their leadership anchored on tenacity and strong personalities, earning them respect and trust (Alberto, 2023). Filipina leaders also demonstrate strength, endurance, and a delicate balance between fierceness and empathy in historically male-dominated fields. They meet challenges head-on and do it with grace and resilience (Dasig, 2020). In the professional field, the experiences of Filipina business

executives show how they manage work and family obligations while displaying flexibility and multitasking skills—qualities that are essential for overcoming prejudice and utilizing cultures of equal opportunity (Osi & Teng-Calleja, 2021).

In terms of communicative practices, Filipina leaders in education promote inclusion and participatory conversations, with an emphasis on transparent interactions that incorporate the opinions of all stakeholders (Alberto, 2023). Communication is an important aspect of empowerment and women leaders learning how to effectively navigate male-dominated fields, employ a nuanced approach to breaking down barriers, and promoting empowerment (Dasig, 2020).

Focusing on cultural aspects, Filipina leaders in a variety of industries are distinguished by their special combination of resilience, empathy, and leadership skills as well as their strong will and strong personality. They are the epitome of the Filipino virtue "pakikipagkapwa," emphasizing social peace and advancement while juggling the competing demands placed on them in the home and workplace. Their leadership and communicative practices are shaped by this cultural background, which makes them particularly successful and culturally relevant. Within the Filipino cultural framework, their tenacity, flexibility, and dedication to constructive change are cherished traits (Alberto, 2023; Dasig, 2020; Osi & Teng-Calleja, 2021).

Communicative Practices of Women Leaders

Women leaders employ different communicative practices to navigate the complexities of their roles. For instance, Madden & Levenshus (2021) emphasized the importance of authentic leadership communication rooted in intersecting identities within

a political training program. In contrast, Zoon & Ashfaq (2022) explored an interaction-based way of creating and performing leadership roles, suggesting that male and female leaders use communication to assert their identities and navigate social expectations.

Women leaders' communicative practices are complex, and shaped by the interaction between sociocultural norms and individual actions. Biddix (2010) used institutional ethnography to provide a lens for examining how societal structures influence women's leadership behaviors, particularly in tech-enabled environments. Similarly, the study by Zeler et al. (2022) showed that gender constructs and cultural norms shape perceptions of women's leadership abilities and communication styles, suggesting that it requires a more in-depth look under cultural and gender lenses which are often overlooked in traditional management theories.

Podcasts as a Communication Medium

According to recent literature, podcasts are recognized as an intimate medium for communication that allows listeners who are physically apart to feel close to one another and overcome obstacles related to context and knowledge. Swiatek (2018) noted the duality of podcasts as a medium that can democratize the production of media or be a space where large media firms can replicate and reinforce existing power structures.

Regarding podcast communicative practices, Hill (2021) noted that vocal performance plays a significant role in message transmission, with nonverbal cues being considered crucial for successful communication in this medium. These cues include paralinguistic behaviors such as tone of voice, pitch, volume, intonation, and rhythm, as well as chronemic behaviors such as speech pace, pausing patterns, response latency,

and overall timing of interactions. The creation of podcasts and the analysis of its episodes, encourage critical thinking and theory application, as it has been used as instructional materials in education to improve engagement and knowledge of communication theories (Taylor & Blevins, 2019).

Finally, examining podcasts may show how they are useful instruments for drawing in larger audiences, promoting thought-provoking conversations about current events, and supporting educational frameworks that support various learning styles (Scriven, 2019). Podcasts' narrative and storytelling elements provide creative means of creating knowledge, making it possible to disseminate information on social and environmental concerns in more accessible ways (Kinkaid, Emard, & Senanayake, 2019).

Chapter III

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study delved into the communicative practices of women IT leaders as observed in podcast narratives through comprehensive lenses. Guided by the Sociocultural Tradition of Communication and leveraging ethnomethodology both as a theory and an approach, the study explored the communicative practices of particular women IT leaders, while also exploring how their views inform these practices and what these practices accomplish in their leadership roles.

Sociocultural Tradition of Communication

The Sociocultural Tradition of Communication (SCT) considers communication as a means by which society is constructed, maintained, or transformed. As Craig (1999) depicted, communication under SCT is "a symbolic process that produces and reproduces shared sociocultural patterns," through the creation, realization, and transformation of social reality (macro-level) and interactions (micro-level). Therefore, SCT indicates that our norms, beliefs, and identities are not given, but are continuously produced and reproduced through communication; thus, binding communities together through shared understanding.

In this context, language plays a significant role in the creation of culture. SCT emphasizes that language serves as the "vehicle" that produces culture and where individuals understand the world. As Littlejohn and Foss (2011) noted, "the process often works the other way round. Our view of reality is strongly shaped by the language we

have used already since we were infants". This illustrates how the relationship between language and culture is two-way, indicating that language actively constructs reality.

Delving deeper into how SCT shapes and transforms the social dynamics of small groups into large societies, Craig (1999) observed how "Our everyday interactions with others depend heavily on preexisting, shared cultural patterns and social structures." Through communication, particularly interactions, societies reproduce existing social orders and "albeit collectively and in the long run, produce the very social order that makes interaction possible in the first place" (ibid).

Finally, SCT also addresses how meanings vary across cultures, akin to semiotics. As discussed by Littlejohn and Foss (2011), contemporary sociocultural theorists assert that "through communication, we get to understand certain things and these shape us as we grow". This emphasizes the impact that communication has in creating shared meanings, especially in different cultures—which is important in a globalized setting.

By highlighting the importance of communicative practices in producing and reproducing social realities and the significance of the two-way relationship between language and culture, SCT illuminates the power of communication in both the creation and the reflection of the world through interactions and social changes.

Ethnomethodology

Moving on to Ethnomethodology, which will serve as both a framework and methodology in this study. Grounded in the sociocultural tradition, ethnomethodology (EM) concentrates on how individuals make sense of their daily lives and navigate their routines. As Marcon & Gopal (2008) discussed, Harold Garfinkel pioneered and laid the foundation by shifting the focus from "what" are to "how" interactions occur.

With that, we dive into the principles surrounding ethnomethodology. Firstly, EM emphasizes the fundamental link between the meanings of words and that of actions. Marcon & Gopal (2008) described this as ***indexicality***, which proposes that "the meaning of a linguistic expression is not unequivocal but rather depends in part on the context in which it is uttered," implying that meanings vary in different social setups.

Another central concept in EM is ***reflexivity***, which refers to "those human practices that serve simultaneously to describe social structures (e.g., rules, institutions) and to constitute them, endowing them with meaning (ibid)." It highlights the two-way relationship between one's actions and/or interactions and the social order, reflecting how reality is both produced and understood through those interactions.

Finally, in EM, ***accountability*** acts as a significant aspect in maintaining understanding and preserving social order (ibid). It underscores how social actions can be seen and communicated, thus compelling individuals to interact with others in a way that said others can comprehend and understand.

Ethnomethodology and the Sociocultural Tradition

Now that we've established Ethnomethodology and its foundation in the Sociocultural tradition, let's dive deeper into the connection between the two. EM focuses more closely on the often-overlooked aspects of social reality that shape our cultures, values, and norms. As Segumpan & Saludadez (2018) put it, "social reality is continually produced and reproduced through everyday interactions," thus challenging the notion that social reality is an external source of one's behavior.

Using different methods, EM practitioners reveal the unspoken rules that govern social interactions. Segumpan & Saludadez (2018) also noted how EM has contributed

to disciplines such as communication studies by focusing on the complexity of culture and social orders. By examining micro-level interactions and communicative practices people use to manifest the social realities in their daily lives, EM highlights the interplay between individual interactions and the social structures where these occur.

Gap in the Knowledge Body

Existing studies explored the representation and dynamics of women leadership within a podcast, but a gap exists in the complex communicative practices employed by these women. Earlier studies have focused primarily on the challenges faced by women leaders and the cultural frameworks they navigate, making their communicative practices and methods unexplored. While podcasts have been perused through a cultural lens and have received considerable attention, the application of an ethnomethodological perspective to dissect the podcast medium remains little. This gap just goes to show the need for an in-depth exploration of the communicative practices of women IT leaders in podcasts through an ethnomethodological lens. This aims to shine a light on their everyday practices that define their leadership and engagements in narratives found in podcast conversations.

Research Questions

With the rationale, literature, and framework introduced, here are the particular inquiries that the study will address:

- What are the views of women IT leaders?
- What are the communicative practices of women IT leaders?
- What do the communicative practices accomplish in leadership?

Chapter IV

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used Ethnomethodology (EM) – as pioneered by Harold Garfinkel which focuses on taken-for-granted practices and "the situated methods and procedures people use to construct sensible and orderly ways of doing things" (Lindolf & Taylor, 2011) – as both framework and methodology. It focuses on the often unspoken and unnoticed practices that people use to make sense and coherence in their everyday interactions. EM is particularly helpful in understanding the "rational, taken-for-granted character of everyday life," methods people use in their daily social interaction, and the way they construct their realities.

To establish the ethnomethodological nature of the study, this inquiry revolved around the "how" of social interactions, particularly how women IT leaders communicate as informed by narratives present in podcast conversations. With the core question of ethnomethodology centering on "How do they do it? Significantly, the it in this case is not the activity as such, but participants' emergent sense of its objectivity, factuality, and orderliness" (ibid). Another important aspect of EM is the concept of having the researcher as the instrument of the study. As Lindolf & Taylor (2011) also highlighted, "EM methods of observation (brief, compared to ethnography), transcription, and interviewing (used least frequently) have been used in studies...". This will bank on the researcher's analytical skills to interpret the data, emphasizing the importance of understanding the context and the participants' perspectives.

Ethnomethodology is different from other research methods due to its emphasis on analyzing conversations. With that, it is assumed that in this study and methodology, the researcher cannot directly observe the conversations as they happen, but it can be observed through the use of podcast as these are recorded conversations. Podcasts offer a creative and practical means to access and explore the interactions as well as the narratives found in them. Through ethnomethodology, the study analyzed the narratives present in the podcast conversations, with the assumption that these narratives reflect their everyday, taken-for-granted interactions.

Participants

When it comes to ethnomethodology, there isn't a strict set of rules for choosing participants because the focus is on observing how people, through their daily interactions, give meaning to things and establish social order. With that, in this study, the participants are selected from a business podcast, which featured business and industry leaders sharing their experiences and advice for young professionals. For anonymity and privacy, it will be referred to as "SS Podcast".

SS Podcast discussed the different facets of career development as well as the challenges and opportunities faced by young professionals. The topics explored in the podcast include measuring progress and success, leveraging technology for building connections, becoming more organized individuals, and choosing the right career path for fresh graduates among many others. The podcast shared stories and insights from impact makers to equip emerging professional with first-hand knowledge in the field.

The SS Podcast piloted its very first episode in May 2021. It is hosted on Spotify (open.spotify.com), an audio streaming app. Zooming in on the platform, it was founded by Daniel Ek and Martin Lorentzon in 2006 and began offering podcasts in 2015 (Gupta, 2021). The episodes chosen for this study include: “Measuring Progress,” which aired in July 2021, featuring the Vice President for Employee Experience of a telecom provider; “Building Connections Through Tech,” aired in March 2022, featuring the Chief Executive Officer of a digital grocery app; “Get Organized,” aired in April 2022, featuring the Chief Executive Officer of an advertising tech firm; and lastly, “Choosing the Right Career Path,” aired in November 2022, with the Executive Vice President of a digital banking company as the guest. The target audience of the podcasts are young professionals and fresh graduates seeking insights into the industry from leaders in the field.

To provide a rich context on how the women IT leaders’ views inform their communicative practices and what they accomplish in their leadership positions through said practices, we focused on episodes featuring women IT leaders. Transcripts from these episodes are tagged to identify each speaker, as outlined in the following table:

Table 1. Episode Participant Guide

TAG	INDUSTRY
WL1	Chief Executive Officer of an advertising tech firm
WL2	Vice President for Employee Experience of a telecom provider
WL3	Chief Executive Officer of a digital grocery app
WL4	Executive Vice President of a digital banking company

Analyzing the discourse of these women leaders gives more insights into the ways in which their views shape their communicative practices and the accomplishments of these practices.

Data Collection

The data were collected by transcribing the particular podcast episodes and capturing the verbal interactions in the podcast conversations featuring women leaders. This allowed the analysis of the communicative practices employed by women leaders, focusing on "how people engage in an activity in ways that implicitly define it for them as that activity" (Lindolf & Taylor, 2011). Observing their interaction during the podcast conversations and describing the context of their talks helped in understanding their communicative practices and how these contribute to their roles as leaders.

Data Analysis

After transcribing the podcast conversations, I analyzed the interactions through an ethnomethodological lens, exploring the nuanced communicative practices of women IT leaders. My focus was on understanding how their views of the sector shape these practices and what they ultimately accomplish in their leadership roles.

For the analysis, I engaged in a process of reading and re-reading the transcripts. As I reviewed the conversations, guided by the research questions, I sought to make sense of what the women leaders were expressing. I asked myself: What do these transcripts reveal about their views? What do they tell me about their communicative practices? And what do they show about their accomplishments as leaders?

As I went through the entire data set, I observed both similar and varying patterns. Throughout the analysis, I moved back and forth between the transcripts, the research questions, and the initial information from the literature. This process helped me identify commonalities in the codes that emerged from the data. I then developed a matrix that linked the transcripts to the codes for each area of inquiry (please refer to Table 2.).

After thoroughly examining the transcripts and coding them based on the themes of views, practices, and accomplishments, I was able to distill the data into relevant themes that addressed the research questions posed earlier.

The next section will present these findings in more detail, revealing the nuanced communicative practices of women IT leaders as reflected in the narratives from the podcast conversations. It will also explore how these practices are informed by their views and what they achieve in their roles as leaders.

Table 2. Matrix of Qualitative Data Analysis

	EXCERPTS	VIEWS OF WOMEN IT LEADERS	COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES OF WOMEN IT LEADERS	ACCOMPLISHMENT IN LEADERSHIP OF THE COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES
WL 1	<p><i>Advertising is a highly competitive industry, and we just want to know, what do you practice to stay on top of every project that you do?</i></p> <p>You know what? What I've done in the last 20 years, like what ### said, is really going into things that I don't know much about. So I've always pursued continuous growth and also learning, because especially now on digital, there's so many things. Before it was the websites, the mobile sites, now it's all the apps. It's all about openness and admitting what you don't know has allowed me to be competitive in the industry and surrounding myself with people who know more than I do.</p> <p>So when I started with ###, guys, I inherited around 80 people, and now there's 102 people in the team now, and people who know more than I do. So I'm learning a lot from them, especially with broadcasts, especially on innovation. So it's really all about openness to developing and gaining new skills and learning about people. On the ### front, I'm learning more about health tech, ad tech, and also fintech. So it's really that learning, openness, and admitting what you don't know.</p>	<p>The industry is continuously changing</p> <p>The industry is unpredictable</p> <p>The industry is diverse, crossing with other industries</p>	<p>Leaders are open to learning</p> <p>Leaders admit what they don't know</p> <p>Leaders continuously developing new skills</p> <p>Leaders join conversation communities who are knowledgeable in IT</p>	<p>Keeping the company stable and relevant</p> <p>Keeping the company competitive</p>

<p>WL 1</p>	<p><i>What's your philosophy when it comes to tackling challenging or complicated tasks? Are you the type to start on it right away, or do you finish the easier ones first?</i></p> <p>You know what, the first thing you have to do is jump right in. So it's either you succeed or you don't. And the idea is to be able to bounce back quickly. So what I've been able to do is really keep my cool, and I go over the facts and remove the subjectivity and the personalities involved. Because that's where you will react to what's happening instead of responding to it.</p> <p>So like what you said, nothing will be perfect, right? Every single thing that we do might have maybe 5, 10, or 50% imperfection. But the way we did it, along with the people that we're working with, will make it even much more, you know, satisfying and fun. That's right.</p> <p>There's a Frozen song, but I never got to see the second one. But what it says is, "Let It Go". Yeah. Because there's always a solution, right? Because there always is. The very first time I started working, I quit after five days. Because I said, wow, this is not the job I want to have.</p>	<p>The industry is unpredictable</p> <p>Success is not about perfection but about finding solutions</p> <p>Success comes from bouncing back quickly from failures</p> <p>The industry is highly competitive</p>	<p>Leaders focus on responding rather than reacting to situations</p> <p>Leaders keep satisfaction and fun in the workplace</p>	<p>Keeping the company stable and relevant</p> <p>Clear decision-making and effective problem-solving</p> <p>Better company performance</p>
<p>WL 1</p>	<p><i>But what do you do when things do not go your way? And how do you cope with it?</i></p> <p>So I asked my parents, oh, you know what, this is what I'm thinking. Because I don't think this is for me. And I said, go ahead. So it's really all about finding another solution. And don't take things</p>	<p>Success is not about perfection but about finding solutions</p> <p>The industry is unpredictable</p>	<p>Leaders keep satisfaction and fun in the company</p> <p>Leaders stress not being hard on oneself and other people</p>	<p>Keeping the company stable and relevant</p> <p>Sustaining effective leadership and resilience</p>

	<p>personally, especially with the people that you're working with. Because sometimes, we don't know what people are going through.</p> <p>Every single people you're going to be working with, sometimes there are times that somebody's in a funk, you're in a funk, or I'm in a funk. So one thing about me is that I actually don't bring everything that we do in the office back home with me. And now that we're always working from home, it's really setting aside time for me to really let go of all of the things.</p> <p>Because again, we can't see what's going to happen next. Look at what happened with the pandemic. So it's really embracing the ambiguity, which is challenging and scary. But that's what we all did in the last two years. So I think we can all do it.</p>	<p>The industry is ambiguous</p> <p>The industry demands adaptability</p>	<p>Leaders focus on objective facts and removing subjectivity</p> <p>Leaders promote empathy and understanding</p> <p>Leaders encourage team cohesion and collaboration</p> <p>Setting boundaries between work and personal life</p>	
<p>WL 1</p>	<p><i>As a leader, what's your style when it comes to delegating tasks to your team members, especially if there's a lot of ambiguity involved?</i></p> <p>Again, another good question. It's evolved along the years. And I always imitate, especially in the beginning of my career, how my other leaders were. And now that I'm older and a little bit wiser, my delegation style has evolved into situational ways of working with people because it's dependent on the team members' knowledge, skills, and capabilities.</p>	<p>The industry is ambiguous</p> <p>The industry demands adaptability</p> <p>The industry is highly collaborative, particularly among other leaders</p>	<p>Leaders adapt their delegation style based on the team members' knowledge, skills, and motivations</p> <p>Leaders use a range of styles from instructional to collaborative decision-making</p> <p>Knowing playing with the strengths of team members</p>	<p>Optimized team performance by leveraging individual strengths</p> <p>More effective goal achievement</p>

	<p>And it doesn't fit all, right? I could be another way with ###, and another way with ###. So I've noticed that my styles have ranged from instructional, acting independently, and deciding together. But out of all of that, it's really enforcing high standards of working.</p> <p>And always with intention because it's really all about sharing your strengths while managing the downsides to achieve the set goals when you're working with your team members, and as well as leaders. Because there are also leaders where you have different strengths. And you have to play with those types of strengths. And especially in our ecosystem, in the ### ecosystem, there's so many leaders, right? And you need to be able to understand how to work with the different leaders that we get to see on a daily, weekly basis.</p>			
<p>WL 1</p>	<p><i>So how do you keep track of all your personalities then? If you said that you're this way with me, for example, and different with someone else. Don't you find that difficult trying to play different parts?</i></p> <p>But like you and I, yes, we are unique. But then there are certain ways that you and I are the same, right? So we need to be able to understand how and what your motivations are. And if your motivation is you want to be the best out of your career, then that's need to be able to work on.</p> <p>For example, one of our leaders inside ### is a new mom. And her first and foremost priority is her family. So you need</p>	<p>The industry is composed of diverse team members</p> <p>The industry demands adaptability</p>	<p>Leaders communicate based on what motivates the team</p> <p>Leaders adjust how they communicate as well as their expectations</p>	<p>Increased commitment and job satisfaction</p> <p>Creates a more engaged workforce</p>

	to understand that as well. So you need to be able to work with what the motivations are , and how they are, and adjust along the way .			
WL 1	<p><i>So can you share one principle in ### that helps you and your team stay organized? Maybe you have like a motto or philosophy that you go by?</i></p> <p>When I started working at ###, that was around February 2021, the team and I revived and redefined our values of ###. So we have five, but I'll tell you what the five are. And I'll choose one that I believe that we are really imbibing, especially now. So we have five values. One is bulletproof bravery, fiery collaboration, super shifter, resource and infinity, and also heart spark. Because we need to have values that we will own.</p> <p>It cannot be the same as the one from ###, because that's all about what ### is all about, right? So on our end, it's all about super shifter. Why? Because working from home has changed the ways of working, right? And we need to be very agile and be on top of the things that we're doing. So we find ways, we find like what you guys were talking about earlier, finding that common ground and seeing how we're going to shift the way we're working with people.</p> <p>For example, on our end, we also changed our business model for our A2P business before we were doing the aggregator work. And now we're doing</p>	<p>The industry is continuously changing</p> <p>The industry requires agility</p> <p>The industry is highly collaborative</p> <p>The industry operates in a remote work environment</p> <p>The industry demands continuous evolution in response to changing conditions</p> <p>Leadership requires collective participation</p>	<p>Leaders leverages organizational values to align the team's actions with the evolving business needs</p> <p>Leaders prioritize agile communication to facilitate rapid shifts</p> <p>Leaders prioritize clear communication to ensure the team is aligned</p> <p>Leaders shift the way they communicate in response to the changes in the industry</p> <p>Leaders involve the entire team in defining organizational values</p>	<p>Foster cohesive work culture and shared values among team members</p> <p>Creating an agile workforce</p> <p>Keeping the company relevant by swiftly adapting to shifts and changes</p> <p>Successfully implement changes in the organization</p>

	<p>direct to sell. So we needed to be agile enough to be able to change it. So December was when we changed it. And now it's been almost two and a half months out of 2022. And the team has been doing really well to be able to do that. So that's one of the things that we want everybody at ### to imbibe is the super shifter.</p> <p>And you know what? These are all done. So we divided everybody into five groups before. This was around April of last year. And every single value that I shared with you was defined by our fire starters. That's what we call our ### people. It was defined by everybody. So we felt like, oh, heart spark, pretty cool, right? When you think about it, because especially now we need to have empathy with everybody that we're working with.</p>			
WL 1	<p><i>So for someone who has yet to learn your ways, what advice would you give self-starters who are struggling with organizing their tasks?</i></p> <p>Self-starters for me are the types of people I want to work with. But having said that, we also need to work with different types of people. But the energy and the enthusiasm of a self-starter is an admirable trait because they're going to hit the ground running. But what I said earlier, we will always get into a funk from time to time, every single person.</p> <p>So even if there is a struggle, what we need to be able to do is identify the issue first. Because if you don't identify it, and</p>	<p>Leaders prefer self-starter, or people who can hit the ground running</p> <p>The industry is composed of diverse team members</p> <p>The industry is continuously changing</p> <p>The needs of the industry are constantly evolving</p>	<p>Leaders prioritize open communication</p> <p>Being solution-oriented by proactively identifying and addressing issues</p> <p>Being open to changes and learning new things</p>	<p>Keeping the company stable and relevant</p> <p>Better company performance</p> <p>Keeping the company competitive through innovation and growth</p>

	<p>you're going to be doing your daily task over and over again, but you don't know what's happening, then that's a problem, not only for yourself, but the people that you get to work with, right?</p> <p>Second is to communicate openly. And that's always what I've told the people at ### is our Slack is open for everybody to come to me and ask me, but I will also talk to your leader because it's a triumvirate wherein it's your leader, myself, and their team member who we're going to be talking to.</p> <p>But if it's a leader, so it's the leader and I, and it's all about communicating properly and then effectively recognizing the steps towards the solution. So we need to put it together and do checkups along the way. And if it doesn't go as planned, then we go back again to the drawing board to do it. And this is something that I've learned from the different leaders I've had along the way.</p> <p>One of the things that my very first leader when I was at ### told me was that always be a sponge. Try to learn as much as I can, but obviously leave the bad things behind, but the good things bring it there. So I've always brought that and up until now, and also embrace change because it's always there.</p>			
<p>WL 2</p>	<p><i>So moving to the corporate side, ###. What are the different types of progress that businesses should track to ensure business sustainability?</i></p>	<p>The industry is continuously changing</p> <p>Technology in the industry changes,</p>	<p>Leaders actively listens to the needs of the customers, anticipating their implicit and explicit needs</p>	<p>Keeping the company competitive</p>

<p>I would probably limit it to three types or three kinds of progress that I think regardless if we are a small enterprise, a medium enterprise, or a large enterprise. The first one is really to focus on your customer satisfaction and customer centricity. Whether the environment change, pandemic, post-pandemic, technology changes, it's very important that we really look at the satisfaction of our customers and we should be able to push for getting to know them beyond what they just demand from us.</p> <p>I will always share the stories of Grab, Airbnb, and all those disruptor organizations or companies. Imagine who would have thought that Airbnb would thrive, even for Grab. The same scenario.</p> <p>Because one factor that makes a growth strategy work immediately is helping everyone understand how their work contributes to the bigger picture. So when people feel that their work matters, they're more invested in it. We're able to really get the buy-in of the people contributing to the greater vision of the organization.</p> <p>I'd like to share as well that I think over the years, I've seen this where, you know, technology changes, the environment changes, competition becomes tougher. But if you're able to really build that very, very strong culture or strong sense of purpose within the organization, regardless of how many hurdles, obstacles, or changes we encounter, we'll be able to thrive in it and succeed as one</p>	<p>regardless if the environment changes with it or not</p> <p>The industry is highly disruptive</p> <p>The industry is highly competitive</p> <p>Buy-in or the agreement of different stakeholders is important in the industry</p> <p>Anticipating customer needs is critical in the industry</p> <p>Success is closely linked to customer satisfaction</p> <p>The industry demands adaptation to changes</p> <p>Culture is an essential factor of success in the industry</p>	<p>Leaders use narratives similar to the value that they would want to communicate</p> <p>Leaders promote shared values among their team</p> <p>Leaders communicate their vision clearly to ensure alignment with their teams</p>	<p>Keeping the company stable and its growth sustainable</p> <p>Keeping the company relevant amidst changes</p>
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	<p>whole group. Yeah, it's the heart really to driving the value add and being able to take care of the customer.</p> <p>It's really the people.</p>			
WL 2	<p><i>Yeah, they improve the overall health of the business. It's really the people. So with that, what is the most efficient way of measuring these different types of progress?</i></p> <p>I'd like to highlight the voice of the customer. I'd like to focus on that. So it's the voice of the customer for external customers.</p> <p>We need to know their pain points. We need to know their wants, their aspirations. So just don't come up with programs or products and services that will just address their pain points, but also anticipate potential future needs.</p> <p>And at the end of the day, these people we took care of, they were the ones who were able to take care of the customers. At the end of the day, similar to your initial question, the fuel, the heart would really be our people. I think the most important part is that they see that you just don't listen, but you act on their feedback.</p>	<p>Success is closely linked to customer satisfaction</p> <p>Initiatives should be highly intentional</p> <p>Employee satisfaction is important in maintaining customer satisfaction</p>	<p>Leaders actively listens to the "voice of the customer" to anticipate their needs</p> <p>Leaders listens to the feedback of their employees</p> <p>Leaders takes necessary actions based on their teams' feedback</p>	<p>Keeping the company stable and its growth sustainable</p>
WL 2	<p><i>So how do we avoid doing busy work that leads to a false sense of productivity?</i></p> <p>I'm a very output-based person. I don't mind not seeing you, especially pre-pandemic. In fact, there were days even last year that I had to give additional</p>	<p>The industry requires flexibility and adaptability</p> <p>Communication and trust are important in</p>	<p>Leaders encourage transparent communication</p>	<p>Keeping the company stable and its growth sustainable</p>

	<p>breaks. At the end of the day, it's really output-based. If you think you worked so much during the weekend and you need a break, then have that break because at the end of the day, the team is not a machine. We are all individuals. We're human beings. We really have to take a break once in a while. Surprisingly, last year, productivity even went up, but in fact, no.</p> <p>So I think the trust, the communication, and just focusing on the output rather than the hours spent will really push people to work smarter. I mean, if you want to do a home errand or a family errand, I'm okay with that for as long as you get the thing delivered on time.</p> <p>Oh yeah, you reminded me of something, ###. In my team, I have a communications arm, sort of my ad agency. Most of the folks assigned in this particular group or pillar are artists. They have to look for the inspiration to get things done. And they are the folks who are up until 4 a.m., 5 a.m. There are instances that they will tell me, I can't attend the morning session because we slept late. Then, it's fine. Wow. We get to respect the working styles for as long as we get things done.</p>	<p>flexible working environments</p>	<p>Leaders actively listens to the needs of their employees</p> <p>Leaders use personal narratives to communicate their point across</p>	
<p>WL 2</p>	<p><i>So, what are the most important hard and soft skills companies should encourage their employees to hold?</i></p> <p>I think right now, focus on hard skills that will really be linked to innovation and entrepreneurial capabilities. It's difficult if you don't have that entrepreneurial</p>	<p>The industry is highly disruptive</p> <p>The industry demands continuous learning</p>	<p>Leaders communicate clearly what values they look for from their team</p> <p>Leaders use personal narratives to</p>	<p>Keeping the company competitive</p> <p>Keeping the company relevant amidst changes</p>

<p>mindset in that innovative mind because competition is really tough. I mentioned earlier that people can just shift from one provider to the other.</p> <p>And if we don't continuously disrupt the way we do things, we really won't survive. So, hard skills-wise, I think those should be related to innovation, so probably something related to technology and entrepreneurial capabilities. But for soft skills, I think this is more important.</p> <p>I mean, even when I talk to recruiters, they will ask me, are there soft skills that you really look for? I will always tell them, you know what? I value soft skills more than hard skills.</p> <p>And when I talk about soft skills, I'm talking about grit, I'm talking about teamwork, I'm talking about the passion. Because at the end of the day, the technical skills of a person can always be learned. But if you don't have the grit, the passion, the "gigil", those are more important skills than, you know, having that innovational entrepreneurial mindset. Because at the end of the day, if you are very, very passionate and you have that grit to create that impact, to make that change that you want to see, those are the things that will really push you.</p> <p>I don't add people to my team who feel that they already know everything. Because at the end of the day, we learn from each other.</p>	<p>The industry is highly competitive, requiring multiple skillset</p> <p>The industry is continuously changing</p>	<p>communicate their point across</p>	
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<p>WL 2</p>	<p><i>So how can companies instill a culture of always wanting to learn and improve?</i></p> <p>It's really walking the talk. I mean, we are both doing a lot of marketing. Regardless of the wonderful campaign that we're able to come up with, if we're not really able to show and let the people feel and experience the kind of culture that we want them to embrace, it's going to be difficult.</p> <p>And I will always say it will have to start with the leaders. Start showing people how things are done. Show how it is done and why it should be done.</p> <p>And every year, if we really want to continuously learn and improve, then show how upping your service or constantly improving yourself, your capabilities, your team's capabilities, then that will really instill that culture of always wanting to learn and improve as an individual or as a team.</p>	<p>Experience is an important factor in the industry</p> <p>The industry demands continuous improvement</p>	<p>Leaders emphasize the importance of leading by example or "walking the talk"</p> <p>Leaders communicate the reason behind the example they set</p>	<p>Keeping the company relevant amidst changes</p>

<p>WL 2</p>	<p><i>What piece of advice would you give a self-starter learning something new that is usually beyond their comfort zone?</i></p> <p>Probably if I am to summarize, number one is start small and just make it a habit. Going out of your comfort zone. I love what ### mentioned earlier, learning inversions. You know, you just have to start small and you just have to make it a habit. My second point is for you to also dream big. I mean, there should always be that long-term goal where you want to be or where you want to go. And then just focus on small progresses. And then the last would be make failure your teacher. That's the beauty of life.</p> <p>And if you just want to continuously learn something new or if you really want to pursue something bigger than yourself or bigger than your comfort zone, just remember this. Great people do things before they're ready. I've never seen any organization or any person who was really able to 100% ready.</p> <p>I remember one teammate of mine said, "Ms. ###, I'm always nervous to speak in front of you." Okay, that's okay because I've gone through that as well. I'm actually an introvert, but I am able to shift myself now. If I need to talk, I can talk. When the job calls for us becoming extroverts, we have to do that and shift. One time, she said, "I want to host".</p> <p>Make it a habit, but dream big.</p>	<p>Success in the industry demands risk-taking</p> <p>Full readiness is somehow elusive in the industry</p> <p>Proactiveness is important to succeed in the industry</p> <p>The industry demands continuous improvement</p> <p>Failure in the industry is viewed as a learning experience</p> <p>The industry requires flexibility and adaptability</p>	<p>Leaders use personal narratives to relate with their team and communicate their point across</p> <p>Leaders shift their communicative practices based on the situation</p> <p>Leaders encourage their audiences to set clear goals</p>	<p>Keeping the company stable and its growth sustainable</p> <p>Keeping the company relevant amidst changes</p> <p>Enable team members to perform effectively</p>
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<p>WL 3</p>	<p><i>What principles do you follow when working with a diverse group of people?</i></p> <p>I think the most important thing to look at is inclusion, right? At the end of the day, if you want to foster an inclusive environment, you have to believe that you're all equals at work, regardless of whatever background you have. Whatever social demographic, if you're male or you're female, whatever school you come from, whatever religion, those don't really matter.</p> <p>What's important is that you have mutual respect. So that's important. And that you create a very transparent environment. So when I work with different people, I make sure that I'm as straightforward, that I'm consistent with how I work with them, regardless of which group. And that consistency becomes important in creating a psychologically safe environment, right? For people to know that they will always be able to share their ideas, that you will be able to accept them, that you don't take anything against them.</p> <p>It's all about how they are at work and how they will be able to deliver on their KPIs and the friendships that you form at work as well. And all in all, if you are able to create that kind of environment, then there's much healthier collaboration. Every person brings a certain set of strengths to the table, and that's what you play around with, basically.</p>	<p>Inclusivity is important to succeed in the industry</p> <p>The industry is composed of diverse individuals</p> <p>The industry is highly collaborative</p>	<p>Leaders promote transparent communication as they create a transparent environment</p> <p>Leaders encourage open communication, allowing team members to share their thoughts and ideas</p> <p>Leaders leverage consistency in interactions to encourage desired behavior</p> <p>Leaders practice clear communication by being straightforward</p>	<p>Promoting healthy collaboration and strong team dynamics</p> <p>Keeping the company stable</p>
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<p>WL 3</p>	<p><i>What do you do to make sure you stay connected with every department of your company?</i></p> <p>I'm glad to say that nowadays, it's easier to stay connected because there's so many channels, right? What I do is I have daily check-ins. It's not necessarily a formal check-in. It's the messages that you send in the morning, throughout the day, that you just check in with people, how they're doing, what's the update on a particular project, just so that they know that you're with them through the day, right? And I have these one-on-ones that are not a project list update. These are just 30-minute meetings.</p> <p>So I may be CEO, but I sit into a lot of the meetings, even meetings where I don't need to be the one to give the decisions or to make the decisions, right? It's just for the team to know that when they're spending a late night on a project, you're there along with them, right? Working on slides, you're there along with them, right? So it's a way of also being connected. And of course, the after-work socials definitely help.</p>	<p>Communication in the industry operates in multiple channels</p> <p>Staying connected with team members is important to succeed</p> <p>Success calls for a hands-on approach in management</p>	<p>Leaders practice open communication</p> <p>Leaders make use of different communication channels to reach their team</p> <p>Leaders set the tone of the day through communication</p> <p>Leaders stay in touch by remaining actively involved in projects and meetings</p> <p>Leaders emphasize staying connected with their team</p>	<p>Promoting higher engagement among team members</p> <p>Keeping the company stable</p> <p>Building the team morale</p>
<p>WL 3</p>	<p><i>What challenges did you encounter as a team that you addressed through technology?</i></p> <p>A lot of our struggles at ### have to do with manual processes and how to you know, I mean, I come from ### as well. So I don't think it's something that's just inherent to ###. An e-grocery platform</p>	<p>The industry integrates manual processes with tech that most of the consumers are not aware of</p>	<p>Leaders use visualization of operations to communicate their points clearly</p>	<p>Keeping the company stable</p> <p>Promoting efficient operations</p>

	<p>actually requires full integration on the back end, on the front end, right?</p> <p>So a lot of the work we do daily requires us to be able to understand what's actually happening on the ground and linking that up with tech. Okay, so for example, in ###, if you order groceries, the app accepts your order. And then it goes to our warehouse, for example, where we have pickers who select your products from the store and pack them and send them to you, right?</p> <p>So there's a lot of manual stuff that happens on the back end that the consumer doesn't see. But at the end of the day, only the consumer will just look at it and say, oh, hey, I need this delivered to me in two hours or three hours, right? So our job is to understand every day what those operational issues are, what those backlogs are, and link them to tech.</p> <p>So that's why we rolled out what's called the ###. So this is our system wherein we're able to actually track the amount of time that is spent by a person to get the goods, to bring it to the cashier, to check it out, to pack it, to dispatch it until it reaches the customer. That's how we're able to address these challenges on an everyday basis. And that's also where we find out, ah, may backlog dito. Oh, this is probably because of the following instances. It's easier to dissect those kinds of problems and address them through tech.</p>	<p>Operations require front-end and back-end integrations</p> <p>Success requires understanding the on-the-ground operations and linking it with tech</p> <p>Success is closely linked to customer satisfaction</p> <p>Success requires thorough data and problem analysis</p> <p>Success is about addressing everyday problems with tech</p>	<p>Leaders break down complex processes to simpler components</p> <p>Leaders leverage data in solving problems</p> <p>Leaders promote a shared goal of addressing customer needs</p>	<p>Keeping the company competitive and relevant</p>
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<p>WL 3</p>	<p><i>So how exactly do you use technology to enhance collaboration at ###?</i></p> <p>Yes, definitely. I think for a tech app, for e-commerce app, it's important to have tech in every part of the business. So tech is highly integrated in the way we do things. It's extremely important now, more than ever, as we're still working from home, right? So ### operates 100% on the cloud, which makes us very, very mobile, right? I mean, we don't even really see each other every day, except maybe for the team that goes to the stores and to the warehouse and check on operations. But for all of us, we're all basically working from home. We use a variety of tools in the management of our statistics, daily stats. We look at those, how we handle our projects. That's also used in tools like Trello, management of all our meetings.</p> <p>And in the way we develop the platform, we're very, very agile. So we have an in-house development team, although some functions are also outsourced, but we're very, very agile in working together, figuring out the enhancements, making changes, troubleshooting, and that all helps us work together because it's very quick. So the open communication lines, each department, you know, telling each other immediately what the problems are from what we see on our tech and our platform, and then using tech as well to solve these issues.</p>	<p>Companies in the industry operates on cloud</p> <p>Mobility is important in the industry</p> <p>The industry is able to operate in a remote setup</p> <p>The industry use a variety of tools for work</p> <p>The industry is highly collaborative</p> <p>The industry is constantly changing and evolving</p>	<p>Leaders practice agility in the way they communicate</p> <p>Leaders leverage open communication, ensuring that issues are quickly identified and resolved</p>	<p>Keeping the company stable</p> <p>Keeping the company relevant</p> <p>Keeping the company operational despite the remote work setup</p>
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<p>WL 3</p>	<p><i>So while building this app, what important lessons have you learned about connecting people with technology and vice versa?</i></p> <p>You know, at the end of the day, to make a platform work, you have to be customer-centric. I think that's the key principle here, right? What's great or ideal on paper doesn't necessarily come out great in execution. So we see that, we learn that every day. So you have to constantly connect to the customer, figure out what their needs are, what the experience is. Believe it or not, I actually read through all of the customer chats that go on to ###. So I know what's up, yeah. Actually, my phone keeps still pinging me every few minutes. That's how I find out what problems or struggles the customer has in interfacing with their app, right? So that's one. And these needs aren't static. They keep changing.</p> <p>You know, when COVID happened, we said, oh, we needed e-grocery to give people access to their household needs in a safe manner. So that was it. We created a platform, right? But nowadays, you know, it's opening back up. It's not just about getting people's needs to them, right? It's all about searchability. What are the other things they can get on the app? How easy it is to find those things? Fulfillment, allowing them to choose when they want things to be delivered.</p> <p>Because now, sometimes they're out, sometimes they're at home, compared to before that they're always at home, right?</p>	<p>Success is strongly linked with customer centricity</p> <p>Ideas doesn't always translate well in execution</p> <p>Success demands constant communication with customers</p> <p>The industry is constantly changing and evolving</p> <p>The industry requires flexibility and adaptability</p> <p>The industry is highly competitive</p>	<p>Leaders leverage open communication</p> <p>Leaders actively listens to the needs and concerns of their customers</p> <p>Leaders emphasize responsiveness by staying connected to customer-accessed channels</p>	<p>Keeping the company relevant</p> <p>Keeping the company sustainable</p> <p>Keeping the company competitive</p>
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	<p>So there's a lot of these needs that you have to be very, very flexible. And if you're customer-centric, you constantly see what your customers, how they're interacting with you, how they're interacting with your competitors, right? Then that helps you constantly be on the move, constantly improve to them, right? Yeah. I think that everyone has been stuck at home for the longest time. So I don't think going to the grocery is top of the list to do once you get up. Yeah.</p>			
<p>WL 3</p>	<p><i>What tips can you give young leaders and self-starters out there to help them work in a team better?</i></p> <p>Oh, that's a good question. People ask me this all the time. Yeah, they ask me, what's your advice to leaders out there? Several. I think one is you have to be able to create and define open communication lines with your team. You need to be approachable to them, right? And related to that is, as mentioned previously, creating a psychologically safe environment. Because nowadays, nobody's really an expert on anything. That's how I look at it.</p> <p>It's an opinion that I have, especially with e-commerce, right? You have such a wide variety of people. You have those that were people who were really into tech from way, way in the beginning, the younger generation. And then you have the more senior ones that come from more established corporate companies that have shifted to tech, bringing the discipline of all their years. So, there's bound to be</p>	<p>Success requires constant learning</p> <p>The industry is composed of diverse individuals</p> <p>Success requires empathy and understanding</p> <p>Success the sum of different functions working together</p> <p>The industry is highly collaborative</p>	<p>Leaders establish open communication channels</p> <p>Leaders encourage team members to share ideas and feedback</p> <p>Leaders leverage the different strengths of team members</p> <p>Leaders utilize virtual communication channels in operations</p> <p>Leaders emphasize celebrating small and big wins</p>	<p>Keeping the company relevant in the fast-changing industry</p> <p>Keeping the company stable</p> <p>Promote better team collaboration</p>

<p>some friction there, right? But if you create a very safe environment, these people, regardless of background, can freely share their ideas and can give each other feedback, which helps both the leader and the team grow, right?</p> <p>And I think there should be respect and empathy for each individual. I talk about empathy because nowadays that's important. Everybody's going through a particular journey and you don't see that because you don't go to the office together, right?</p> <p>Yeah, agree. And most of your Zoom meetings are really going through the motions, going through all of the things you have to achieve, things you have to deliver, right? So, there needs to be that embedded empathy in each of us and an appreciation of what each person can bring to the team and you supplement and complement those strengths with those of the other people in the team, right?</p> <p>And the leaders, I always tell my team that the ability of a leader also lies in being able to see what those strengths are and put them all together so that the sum is greater than the part, right? And lastly, to be able to recognize the small wins and the big wins. It's not always perfect, you know? Like even for us running an e-commerce platform, every day is a challenge. There seems to be a war that we're fighting every day, whether it's internal or external, right? But we make it a point to recognize those small wins</p>			
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	<p>and, of course, celebrate the big wins and that matters a lot to keep the team motivated, right? So, I think those things.</p>			
<p>WL 4</p>	<p><i>In your experience, how did you know that being in HR is the best career path for you?</i></p> <p>Yeah, I agree. So I started a career in engineering. I was in process engineering. I would create experiments to increase the yield and productivity of the output, right? So it was very technical. I had to deal with machines. I had to deal with re-engineering the process. I did a lot of math on the job and, of course, process improvement. But at the center of it are people. And when you introduce change in technology, in the manufacturing, I was in the manufacturing sector at the time. At the heart of it are people.</p> <p>And when I introduce changes in technology and process improvement, it cannot be without a focus on people and how they would accept the change. And that's number one. Two, how will this impact the change in their roles and their jobs? And so, I solutioned for that as well. And so, that became the springboard for leaders of the organization to notice me and how I could actually influence people to change. Because I created programs and I created the change impact plan and framework for moving from point A to point B. So, I was offered a career in HR. Recreation development. And I did that for a couple of years. But I went back to quality assurance.</p>	<p>Success accounts for the people</p> <p>The industry demands continuous learning</p> <p>The industry is continuously changing</p> <p>The industry is continuously evolving, in need of constant upgrade</p> <p>Digital transformation is closely linked with people transformation</p>	<p>Leaders practice change communication, balancing the both the technical and people aspects of the change</p> <p>Leaders emphasize continuous learning and self-improvement</p> <p>Leaders practice behavior change communication, focusing on influencing change in mindsets</p>	<p>Keeping the company stable</p> <p>Keeping the company relevant in fast-evolving industry</p> <p>Fostering collaboration and strong team dynamics</p>

<p>When I became an expat in Singapore, I did both technical and HR management consulting. And when I came back to the country and found a job in ###, I was in HR already. So, there were a lot of initiatives started out of changes in technology, in financial services, and our digital transformation in ### had a lot of influences from the tech side or the digital side. But I'm very comfortable with that because maybe of my engineering background. So, part of the story of ### digital transformation is the people transformation as well. And being able to lead teams, groups towards transformation of being agile at scale and digital to the core. (...)</p> <p>So, you said, you know, your engineering is very far from the HR discipline. Well, that's true in a lot of sense. But you know, I taught myself and others taught me, right? So, I think what I want to point out from that is you don't stop learning. You need to be lifelong learners because even if you took up a course in the university, a three-year, four-year, five-year course, those have an expiration date. You have to constantly upgrade and you have to constantly learn. You have to constantly feed yourself with new things. You never stop regardless of what age you are in.</p> <p>So the HR profession was very interesting for me because at some point, it became very hard also to deal with people. It's not always easy. Everyone has their own ways, right? But how do you make them cooperate? How do you make them</p>			
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	<p>collaborate? How do you make them follow? How do you make them grow? How do you make them think of something differently, right? And change mindsets. So that became very fascinating to me. And for me, when you shape the structure, that's very engineering.</p>			
WL 4	<p><i>What other aspects of a career should an individual consider before diving into that specific job?</i></p> <p>Yeah, so you have to do your research and find out more about the organization. So I think one important aspect is culture, the culture of the organization. Culture is really about how things are done in the organization, what are the shared beliefs and values of the leaders and the people in the organization. Learn about the culture and ask questions about it. It will give you an idea if you will thrive in that work environment by knowing the culture.</p> <p>I think the next one we talk about lifelong learning is training and development, more development. Will the organization invest in developing you? How do employees get trained or gain access to courses? Is there a coaching and mentoring program in place? So you can ask that from the organization. You can also ask about career paths and promotion. Does the company promote people and how often, right? And then I think the pay is important and well-paid.</p>	<p>The industry is continuously changing</p> <p>Success comes from making people understand why changes are important</p> <p>Fear of change is inevitable</p> <p>Success demands lifelong learning</p> <p>Training and development address the skill gap caused by the company changes</p>	<p>Leaders practice transparent communication, addressing concerns and providing needed support</p> <p>Leaders make sure that visions are aligned</p> <p>Leaders practice proactive background research</p> <p>Leaders learn the facts by asking questions</p> <p>Leaders practice positive feedback and recognition to encourage desired behavior</p>	<p>Keeping the company stable</p> <p>Keeping the company adaptable and relevant</p> <p>Keeping the company open and not resistant to change</p>

<p>(...) Yeah, so I think it's important to tell people what is the change that's happening and help them recognize what it is about. So it's common for people to ignore the change for various reasons. So one is, I'm okay, nothing is broken, so why should I change, right? Or some know that there is already a burning reason to change, but they are apathetic to it because of the fear of dealing with the change itself.</p> <p>So as a leader, it's important for people in your team to understand why there is a need to change, explain the reasons behind the change, including the issues, pain points, and the direction of the organization. So as a leader, we must give people an opportunity to ask questions and make suggestions how to go about the change. Of course, it's important to address their concerns and show people how the change benefits them personally. Provide training and coaching also to help employees know what the need is, what is needed, rather, to shift or what they need to do to ensure that the change is successful and address any skill gaps.</p> <p>While you're undergoing the change, also use positive feedback and recognition to encourage people toward the new way.</p> <p>So, leadership, being a leader is a big responsibility. You have to take people along with you. And I think for many of the graduates, that should be part of the ambition, right? In looking for a career.</p>			
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	From being an individual contributor, how else can you grow to become a really good leader?			
WL 4	<p><i>How does ### utilize tech to push the agenda of people and learning?</i></p> <p>When we moved from banking to being a tech company with a banking franchise, we wanted to bring people along, take everyone along with us. So that's the line, no one gets left behind. The technology that we embrace has become significant to the banking business, to our business, because it is a tool to complement people at work. So it helps us enhance our jobs, makes us productive and unburden people from manual work. More importantly, it helps us improve not just the employee experience, but the customer experience for our banking services. So that said, technology has become part of the human condition, right? In this case, for customers and our employees, it helps in enabling us. So we use technology as tools, right? So therefore, people have to be literate about technology and use it as a tool to manage processes, create and communicate information, provide services. Because of the technology developments in the financial services sector, we actually encourage our people to learn it.</p> <p>So we have an open learning system, you can enroll in courses, even if it's not in your own domain. We have a corporate university, we call it ### that doesn't offer</p>	<p>Success is linked with customer and people experiences</p> <p>The industry is constantly changing and evolving</p> <p>Technology reduces manual work in the industry</p> <p>Tech complements people</p> <p>Tech is viewed as a tool to manage process, transmit info, and provide services</p> <p>Success demands being good with more than one domain</p> <p>Success requires partnership with different sectors</p> <p>The industry is highly collaborative</p>	<p>Leaders promotes belonging by using inclusive language</p> <p>Leaders use personal stories to get their point across</p> <p>Leaders promote using tech not only for internal but also for societal development</p> <p>Leaders leverage partnerships among different sectors</p> <p>Leaders promote the use of technology as a tool to enhance work processes</p>	<p>Keeping the company stable</p> <p>Contribute to nation-building and development</p>

<p>just banking courses, but tech courses. So we have a term, how do we develop people? We want them to be hashtag talents (#TALENTS). #TALENTS, you're not only good in one domain, you can learn two or three domains. We even put up an initiative, the ###, where we have, through our CSR initiative, partnered with schools and universities to offer free courses in technology, and have recently put up in partnership with a partner in Singapore the ###, where we teach different sectors of government, different sectors from private and government entities, their leaders. We've offered a course on digital transformation. So this is in line with ###.</p> <p>So the ### aspect of people development does not reside only internally with our people, but we have expanded it, that reach to various communities outside the bank. We're doing it not because of our higher purpose. So the purpose of the bank is co-creating innovations for a better world, right? And we cannot be inward looking. We should be outward looking. And banking does not just exist to give financial services, but it also exists to help develop economies that's the higher purpose, right? So we want to be part of nation building and financial inclusion. Yeah, so that's the thinking behind the ### movement that we're trying to espouse or create in line with the communities where we serve.</p>			
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<p>WL 4</p>	<p><i>Even our young professionals who already have like one to two years of experience, you know, but still undecided about their career path. So what would be your ultimate advice to them?</i></p> <p>I think it's important to be thinking of your future. Your future is very important where it's headed. And the earlier you start taking a dive, even if you are uncertain, you know, the world, the VUCA world, I'm sure you know about that. There is no certainty. The only thing that's constant is change. I think you need to be courageous, you know, just go for the interviews, go for a job and be employed, you know, but also at the same time, keep your eyes on the future, work on your goals and keep developing yourself. That's really important. What is very hard is to be stagnant, to get stuck. I think the job market now, especially, you know, it's safer to go out, you know, not like when we were all in the lockdown, right?</p> <p>It's very hard to find a job or to start something. But today, you know, companies are opening up and even in the back, we are looking for talents, right? But sometimes talents are a bit choosy. But, you know, if you wait, right? And not dive into it, I think it will set you back. It will be to the disadvantage, to your disadvantage because you're not learning and growing. Every day counts, I think.</p>	<p>Success requires forward-thinking or a futures mindset</p> <p>The industry is uncertain and ambiguous</p> <p>The industry is constantly changing</p> <p>Success demands consistent development</p> <p>Success demands risk-taking</p>	<p>Leaders encourage having goals for the future</p> <p>Leaders promote proactiveness and notes the danger of being stagnant</p>	<p>Keeping the company relevant</p> <p>Keeping the company profitable</p> <p>Keeping the company adaptable to uncertain changes</p>
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Ensuring Plausibility

Finally, to ensure the plausibility of the findings, both empirical plausibility and theoretical plausibility are employed. "It is easier to accept an association as causal when there is a rational and theoretical basis for such a conclusion" ("Bradford Hill Criteria," 2010). For empirical plausibility, the findings were compared to trends in the industry and the researcher's real-world experiences in professional settings led by women, aiming to evaluate if the findings make sense to the participants of the study. On the other hand, theoretical plausibility will involve comparing the findings with literature (such as existing journals and research) on communicative practices in professional settings, assessing if the findings from the ethnomethodological analysis align with universal communicative practices of women IT leaders.

Chapter V

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aimed to answer three research questions: (1) what are the views of women IT leaders; (2) what are the communicative practices of women IT leaders; and (3) what do the communicative practices accomplish in leadership.

Views of Women IT Leaders

Based on the findings in this study, the views of women IT leaders reflect their industries' complex and dynamic nature. These views are detailed below.

The industry is continuously changing, evolving, and disruptive.

These women leaders navigate the disruptiveness of IT in their respective industries. Particularly WL1 as the CEO of an advertising-tech firm oversaw the shift of their business model from being an aggregator to a direct-to-sell approach.

*“For example, on our end, **we also changed our business model** for our A2P business before we were doing the aggregator work. And now we're doing direct-to-sell. So **we needed to be agile enough to be able to change it**. So December was when we changed it. And now it's been almost two and a half months out of 2022. And the team has been doing really well to be able to do that. So that's one of the things that we want everybody at ### to imbibe is the super shifter.” [WL1-01]*

WL2, on the other hand, highlighted how initiated changes in the business environment, together with the shifts brought about by technological advancements, should go back to serving the customers amidst these changes.

*“I would probably limit it to three types or three kinds of progress that I think regardless if we are a small enterprise, a medium enterprise, or a large enterprise. The first one is really to focus on your customer satisfaction and customer-centricity. **Whether the environment change, pandemic, post-pandemic, technology changes**, it's very important that we really look at the satisfaction of our customers and we should be able to push for **getting to know them** beyond what they just demand from us.”*

[WL2-01]

As the CEO of a digital grocery app, WL3 observed how the services they offer should respond to customer needs. From serving people who were always at home, they needed to shift to serving people who were out of their homes.

*“You know, when COVID happened, we said, oh, we needed e-grocery to give people access to their household needs in a safe manner. So that was it. We created a platform, right? But nowadays, you know, it's opening back up. It's not just about getting people's needs to them, right? **It's all about searchability**. What are the other things they can get on the app? How easy it is to find those things? **Fulfillment, allowing them to choose when they want things to be delivered.**”* *[WL3-01]*

Changes in tech also affect people. WL4 highlighted the need to take note of the people aspect of technological changes, making them understand the impact of these changes on their roles in the company.

*“And when you **introduce change in technology**, in the manufacturing, I was in the manufacturing sector at the time. At the heart of it are people. And **when I introduce changes in technology and process improvement, it cannot be without a focus on people and how they would accept the change.** And that's number one. Two, how will this impact the change in their roles and their jobs? And so, I solutioned for that as well. And so, that became the springboard for leaders of the organization to notice me and how I could actually influence people to change.” [WL4-01]*

Trial and error are also seen as an important factor. WL1 stated how endeavors undertaken in the industry can have some imperfections, demanding changes in approach to find the right solution.

*“You know what, the first thing you have to do is jump right in. So it's either you succeed or you don't. And the idea is **to be able to bounce back quickly.** (...) So like what you said, **nothing will be perfect, right?** Every single thing that we do might have maybe 5, 10, or 50% imperfection. (...) Because **there's always a solution, right? Because there always is.**” [WL1-02]*

As the VP for employee experience, WL2 observed how technology and the business environment change, making the industry more competitive. She emphasized having a strong culture to thrive in this competitive business landscape.

*“I'd like to share as well that I think over the years, I've seen this where, you know, **technology changes, the environment changes, competition becomes tougher.** But if you're able to really build that very, very strong culture or **strong sense of purpose** within the organization, regardless of how many hurdles, obstacles, or changes we encounter, we'll be able to thrive in it and succeed as one whole group.” [WL2-02]*

From being stay-at-home, WL3 observed their customer starting to come out when the pandemic started subsiding. This prompted them to be flexible to serve the changing and evolving demands of the market given the changes in the environment.

*“Because now, sometimes they're out, sometimes they're at home, compared to before that they're always at home, right? So there's a lot of these needs that **you have to be very, very flexible.** And if you're customer-centric, you constantly see what your customers, how they're interacting with you, how **they're interacting with your competitors,** right? Then that helps you constantly be on the move, constantly improve to them, right?” [WL3-02]*

As an EVP of a digital bank, WL4 emphasized the need for lifelong learning given that knowledge gained before might not be applicable now and that one must constantly upgrade to cope with these changes and evolution in the industry.

*“So, you said, you know, your engineering is very far from the HR discipline. Well, that's true in a lot of sense. But you know, I taught myself and others taught me, right? So, I think what I want to point out from that is you don't stop learning. You **need to be lifelong learners** because even if you took up a course in the university, a three-year, four-year, five-year course, **those have an expiration date**. You have to **constantly upgrade** and you have to constantly learn. You have to constantly feed yourself with new things. You never stop regardless of what age you are in.” [WL4-02]*

WL2 emphasized the need to disrupt the way they do things in the industry in order to survive, demanding an innovative and entrepreneurial mindset.

*“And **if we don't continuously disrupt the way we do things, we really won't survive**. So, hard skills-wise, I think those should be related to innovation, so probably something related to technology and entrepreneurial capabilities. But for soft skills, I think **this is more important**.” [WL2-03]*

Moreover, WL2 committed to lifelong learning, seeing learning as a journey needed to be travelled in order to cope with how things and the environment change.

*“It's a journey. And I'm going to tell you now, even if I think I reach the senior citizen age, **I will continue to learn things**. And that is the most important thing. Because it's going to be a journey. Things are changing, the environment is changing. If we believe too*

much in ourselves, that we know everything, and that we can't learn anything anymore, then it will really lead to extinction.” [WL2-04]

WL3 highlighted that no one can really be an expert in anything, particularly in the e-commerce industry. Generational difference also contributes to the evolving business landscape where leaders need to work with a variety of people with different working styles and points of view.

*“And related to that is, as mentioned previously, creating a psychologically safe environment. Because nowadays, **nobody's really an expert on anything**. That's how I look at it. It's an opinion that I have, especially with e-commerce, right? **You have such a wide variety of people**. You have those that were people who were really into tech from way, way in the beginning, the younger generation. And then you have the more senior ones that come from more established corporate companies that have shifted to tech, bringing the discipline of all their years.” [WL3-03]*

In line with those points, WL4 had a similar notion, emphasizing the need to be lifelong learners. This is link with the belief that one must constantly upgrade and learn new things regardless of one's age. (Refer to **WL4-02** for more context.)

These women IT leaders saw the rapid pace of tech advancements and the disruptive nature of the industry. Fear of change is a common challenge, as the industry is often uncertain and ambiguous. In the same vein, women IT leaders view the industry as a highly competitive and disruptive field, requiring constant change and upgrades to remain relevant.

They also view continuous learning and development as necessities in the industry. Given the constant change and need for adaptability, they see that success demands lifelong learning, consistent development, and ongoing training to address skill gaps. These women IT leaders see experience as a crucial factor in navigating industry changes, understanding that digital transformation is closely linked with people transformation.

The industry requires flexibility, adaptability, and agility.

Recalling her experience from previous years, WL1 observed how one can never know the future and that as leaders they should embrace ambiguity, being able and ready to adapt and be flexible to future changes or challenges.

*“And now that we’re always working from home, it’s really **setting aside time for me** to really let go of all of the things. Because again, **we can’t see what’s going to happen next**. Look at what happened with the pandemic. So it’s really **embracing the ambiguity**, which is challenging and scary. But that’s what we all did in the last two years. So I think we can all do it.” [WL1-03]*

As an introvert herself, WL2 saw the need to be able to adapt and shift in response to the demands of their roles as leaders. Being ready to shift, when the job calls for it.

“I remember one teammate of mine said, “Ms. ###, I’m always nervous to speak in front of you.” Okay, that’s okay because I’ve gone through that as well. I’m actually an introvert, but I am able to

*shift myself now. **If I need to talk, I can talk. When the job calls for us becoming extroverts, we have to do that and shift.*** [WL2-05]

In the e-commerce space, WL3 highlighted the need to be flexible to respond to the changing needs of the customers. Particularly with the shift from being always at home to being able to go out from their houses, prompting the shift in market demands as well. (Refer to excerpt **WL3-02** for more context.)

Being in digital banking, WL4 saw the need to develop talents that are capable in more than one domain. Beyond banking courses, she promoted learning tech courses to be knowledgeable in both areas, highlighting the adaptability needed in her sector.

*"We have a corporate university, we call it ### that doesn't offer just banking courses, but tech courses. So we have a term, how do we develop people? We want them to be hashtag talents (#TALENTS). **#TALENTS, you're not only good in one domain, you can learn two or three domains.*** [WL4-03]

Being in a creative field such as advertising-tech firm, WL1 emphasized the need to be able to shift the way they work based on the people they are working with.

*"It **cannot be the same** as the one from ###, because that's all about what ### is all about, right? So on our end, it's all about super shifter. Why? Because **working from home has changed the ways of working**, right? And we **need to be very agile and be on top of the things** that we're doing. So we find ways, we find like what you guys were talking about earlier, **finding that common ground***

*and seeing how we're going to **shift the way we're working with people.*** [WL1-04]

Likewise, WL1 also highlighted the need to change and adapt as a whole business in order to respond to the changing market demands. Particularly, shifting from one approach to a different business model. (Refer to **WL1-01** for more context.)

Similar to WL1, WL2 also emphasized pursuing things bigger than one comfort zone, highlighting how individuals and organizations alike can never be 100% ready.

“And then the last would be make failure your teacher. That's the beauty of life. (...) And if you just want to continuously learn something new or if you really want to pursue something bigger than yourself or bigger than your comfort zone, just remember this. Great people do things before they're ready. I've never seen any organization or any person who was really able to 100% ready.”
[WL2-06]

Women IT leaders highlighted the importance of flexibility, adaptability, and agility in navigating the unpredictable nature of the industry. Being capable in multiple domains and anticipating challenges are also crucial attributes for success. To thrive in this environment, they see it is essential to embrace risk-taking, be open to ambiguity, and possess a forward-thinking mindset.

Success is defined by resilience and problem-solving.

Both WL1 and WL2 shared the same ideas on failure. The former highlighted bouncing back from setbacks and understanding that nothing is perfect, and that there

will always be a solution to a problem; while the later emphasized making failure one's teacher stating how both people and businesses can never be fully ready and there's a need to do things before one is ready. (Refer to **WL1-02** and **WL2-06** for more context.)

Crafting solutions for problems in the e-commerce space, WL3 observed that sometimes there's a gap between theory and practice and that to make a platform work, it should be focused on the needs of the customers.

*"You know, at the end of the day, **to make a platform work, you have to be customer-centric.** I think that's the key principle here, right? **What's great or ideal on paper doesn't necessarily come out great in execution.** So we see that, we learn that every day. So you have to **constantly connect to the customer, figure out what their needs are, what the experience is.**" [WL3-04]*

On the other hand, WL4 further emphasized the need to be courageous in the face of constant change, being ready to face setback but still working towards the future by improving oneself every day.

*"There is no certainty. The **only thing that's constant is change.** I think you need to be courageous, you know, just go for the interviews, go for a job and be employed, you know, but also at the same time, **keep your eyes on the future, work on your goals and keep developing yourself.** That's really important." [WL4-04]*

With complex operations, WL3 is prone to solving problems in the processes they have in their company, and that problem-solving in their field requires understanding both the human and tech factors that are in play.

*“So a lot of the work we do daily **requires us to be able to understand what's actually happening on the ground and linking that up with tech.** Okay, so for example, in ###, if you order groceries, the app accepts your order. And then it goes to our warehouse, **for example, where we have pickers who select your products from the store and pack them and send them to you, right? So there's a lot of manual stuff that happens on the back end that the consumer doesn't see.** But at the end of the day, only the consumer will just look at it and say, oh, hey, I need this delivered to me in two hours or three hours, right? So our job is to **understand every day what those operational issues are, what those backlogs are, and link them to tech.** So that's why we rolled out what's called the ###. So this is our system wherein we're able to **actually track the amount of time that is spent** by a person to get the goods, to bring it to the cashier, to check it out, to pack it, to dispatch it until it reaches the customer. That's how we're able to **address these challenges on an everyday basis.**” [WL3-05]*

These women IT leaders view success as a combination of resilience and problem-solving. They recognize that perfection is often elusive and that failures can be valuable learning experiences. Success requires a willingness to take risks, continuously develop skills, and excel in multiple domains. They also see that problem-solving is often driven by data. Understanding that both technology and human operations are vital for driving effective solutions and ensuring success for their company.

The industry is diverse and highly collaborative.

People have unique motivations and leaders must understand these, just as WL1 articulated. In line with that, she also stated the need to work with people who have different ways of working.

*“But like you and I, yes, **we are unique**. But then there are **certain ways that you and I are the same**, right? So we need to be able to **understand how and what your motivations are**. (...) But having said that, we also **need to work with different types of people**. But the energy and the enthusiasm of a self-starter is an admirable trait because they're going to **hit the ground running**. But what I said earlier, we will always get into a funk from time to time, every single person.” [WL1-05]*

On the other hand, WL3 highlighted impact of inclusion and seeing each other as equals, regardless of gender, beliefs, and backgrounds.

*“I think the **most important thing to look at is inclusion**, right? At the end of the day, if you want to foster an inclusive environment, you have to believe that you're all equals at work, regardless of whatever background you have. Whatever social demographic, if you're male or you're female, whatever school you come from, whatever religion, those don't really matter. [WL3-06]*

WL1 also emphasized how people, more than having unique motivations, also have unique strengths. Leaders should play into these diverse strength and be able to understand how leaders like them work and be ready to collaborate with them.

*“Because there are also leaders where you have different strengths. And you have to **play with those types of strengths**. And especially in our ecosystem, in the ### ecosystem, there’s so many leaders, right? And you need to be able to **understand how to work with the different leaders** that we get to see on a daily, weekly basis.” [WL1-06]*

Collaboration among teams is anchored on their communication being agile. As WL3 highlighted, in her team, they are agile in working together, making changes, and troubleshooting to solve problems.

*“And in the way we develop the platform, we’re very, very agile. So we have an in-house development team, although some functions are also outsourced, but we’re very, very **agile in working together**, figuring out the **enhancements, making changes, troubleshooting**, and that all helps us work together because it’s very quick. So the **open communication lines**, each department, you know, **telling each other immediately what the problems are from what we see on our tech and our platform**, and then using tech as well to solve these issues.” [WL3-07]*

As an EVP, WL4 highlighted the need to collaborate beyond the walls of their company. She emphasized the need to be able to work with both private and public sectors and reaching communities outside the confines of the digital bank.

*“We even put up an initiative, the ###, where we have, through our CSR initiative, **partnered with schools and universities** to offer*

*free courses in technology, and have recently put up in partnership with a partner in Singapore the ###, where we teach different sectors of government, different sectors from private and government entities, their leaders. (...) So the ### aspect of people development does not reside only internally with our people, but we have expanded it, that **reach to various communities outside the bank.**" [WL4-05]*

Women IT leaders view the industry as a diverse and collaborative ecosystem. With collective leadership and remote work arrangements becoming the norm, they see inclusivity as a factor in fostering a collaborative environment. They see the importance of partnering with various sectors and working with diverse teams to achieve success.

Customer-centricity and satisfaction is important in the industry.

Being in the telecom sector, WL2 emphasized how programs, products, and services should focus on the customers and address their pain points and needs.

*"I'd like to highlight the **voice of the customer.** I'd like to focus on that. So it's the voice of the customer for external customers. We need to know their pain points. We need to know their wants, their aspirations. **So just don't come up with programs or products and services that will just address their pain points, but also anticipate potential future needs.**" [WL2-07]*

Similarly, WL3 highlighted the need to be connected to the customers to get to know their needs and experiences in the platform. (Refer to **WL3-04** for more context.)

WL3 also mentioned about engaging directly with customers, reading their feedback firsthand in order to address their needs and improve their experiences.

*Believe it or not, **I actually read through all of the customer chats that go on to ###.** So I know what's up, yeah. Actually, my phone keeps still pinging me every few minutes. That's **how I find out what problems or struggles the customer has in interfacing with their app**, right? So that's one. And these needs aren't static. They keep changing.” [WL3-08]*

While WL4, linked elevated employee experiences to better customer experiences. She also highlighted how technology plays a crucial role in improving both experiences, particularly in reducing manual work and processes.

*“The technology that we embrace has become significant to the banking business, to our business, because it is a **tool to complement people at work**. So it helps us enhance our jobs, makes us productive and **unburden people from manual work**. More importantly, it **helps us improve not just the employee experience, but the customer experience** for our banking services. So that said, **technology has become part of the human condition**, right?” [WL4-06]*

Women leaders view customer-centricity and satisfaction (understanding customer needs, anticipating their expectations, and delivering exceptional experiences) as important factors of success. In line with this, women leaders saw the need for effective

communication, empathy, and a deep understanding of both tech and people factors that influence customer satisfaction.

Synthesis of the Views of Women IT Leaders

To interpret the views of the women IT leaders, codes were identified and assigned as views on the industry. The table below summarizes these insights.

Table 3. Summary of the Views of Women IT Leaders

The industry is continuously changing, evolving, and is disruptive.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The industry is constantly changing and evolving • The industry is continuously changing • The industry is highly competitive • Fear of change is inevitable • The industry is uncertain and ambiguous • The industry is highly disruptive • Technology in the industry changes, regardless if the environment changes with it or not • The industry demands continuous evolution in response to changing conditions • The industry is continuously evolving, in need of constant upgrade • The industry demands continuous improvement • The industry demands continuous learning • Success demands lifelong learning • Success requires constant learning • Success demands consistent development • Digital transformation is closely linked with people transformation • Experience is an important factor • Training and development address the skill gap caused by the company changes
The industry requires flexibility, adaptability, and agility.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The industry demands adaptability • The industry demands adaptation to changes • The industry requires flexibility and adaptability • Success demands risk-taking • The industry is ambiguous • The industry requires agility • Success demands being good with more than one domain • Success requires forward-thinking or a futures mindset • Full readiness is somehow elusive
Success is defined by resilience and problem-solving.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Success is not about perfection but about finding solutions • Ideas doesn't always translate well in execution • Failure in the industry is viewed as a learning experience • Success demands risk-taking • Success demands consistent development • Success requires thorough data and problem analysis • Success comes from bouncing back quickly from failures • Success requires being good with more than one domain

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Success the sum of different functions working together • Success comes from making people understand why changes are important • Success requires understanding the on-the-ground operations and linking it with tech
<p>The industry is diverse and highly collaborative.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Success requires partnership with different sectors • The industry is diverse, crossing with other industries • The industry is composed of diverse team members • The industry is composed of diverse individuals • The industry is highly collaborative • Inclusivity is important to succeed • Leadership requires collective participation • The industry is highly collaborative, particularly among other leaders • The industry operates in a remote work environment
<p>Customer-centricity and satisfaction is important in the industry.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Success is closely linked to customer satisfaction • Success demands constant communication with customers • Success is linked with customer and people experiences • Success requires thorough data and problem analysis • Anticipating customer needs is critical • Success accounts for the people • Success requires empathy and understanding • Success requires understanding the on-the-ground operations and linking it with tech

To address the first research question— what are the views of women IT leaders—five key themes have emerged:

1. The industry is continuously changing, evolving, and is disruptive.
2. The industry requires flexibility, adaptability, and agility.
3. Success is defined by resilience and problem-solving.
4. The industry is diverse and highly collaborative.
5. Customer-centricity and satisfaction are important in the industry.

Communicative Practices of Women IT Leaders

Based on the findings in this study, the communicative practices of women IT leaders demonstrate their proactiveness in their professional development, flexibility in their leadership style, transparency in their interactions, understanding of their team's

needs, and focus on using data and technology to improve customer experience. These communicative practices are detailed below.

Women leaders practice continuous learning and self-improvement.

Being in the industry for quite some time, WL1 highlighted continuous learning particularly in the digital era. She emphasized the openness and willingness to learn from more knowledgeable individuals.

*“You know what? What I've done in the last 20 years, like what ### said, is really going into things that I don't know much about. So I've always pursued **continuous growth and also learning**, because especially **now on digital**, there's so many things. Before it was the websites, the mobile sites, now it's all the apps. It's all about **openness** and admitting what you don't know has allowed me to be competitive in the industry and **surrounding myself with people who know more than I do.**” [WL1-07]*

Similarly, WL2 expressed her commitment to lifelong learning and not limiting herself to what she already knows, understanding that the business landscape is continuously changing. (Refer to excerpt **WL2-04** for more context.) In addition, WL2 also articulated how leading by example is important in fostering a culture of learning, showing her team how she herself is committed to learning and improvement.

*“And every year, if we really want to **continuously learn and improve**, then show how upping your service or constantly improving yourself, your capabilities, your team's capabilities, then*

that will really instill that culture of always wanting to learn and improve as an individual or as a team.” [WL2-08]

Both WL3 and WL4 emphasized how no one can be experts in everything and that there's a need to constantly upgrade, understanding that whatever they might have learned can be obsolete in the future. (Refer to **WL3-03** and **WL4-02** for more context.)

The communicative practices of these women IT leaders puts a strong emphasis on continuous learning and self-improvement. They demonstrate a willingness to learn new things, admit their knowledge gaps, and actively develop new skills. They are also open to change and embrace the opportunity to learn from new experiences, as well as, encourage their team members to set goals for the future and practice proactive research, fostering a culture of growth and development within their organizations.

Women leaders practice adaptability and situational leadership.

Both WL1 and WL2 shared about the importance of being adaptable. While WL1 emphasized adapting the ways of working based who you're working with, WL2 on the other hand, emphasized being adaptable enough to be able to shift you own ways of working, should the job call for such a shift. (For more context on this, refer to excerpts **WL1-04** and **WL2-05**.)

Similarly, WL4 practiced situation-based leadership, particularly in making people understand specific situations, i.e., rolling out tech changes. Her response to the situation calling for effective change communication was later on recognized by her leaders. (Refer to excerpt **WL4-01** for more context.)

Coming a from a field that combines complex on-the-ground and backend integrations with customer frontend application, WL3 emphasized the need to stay agile in order to adapt to situations that needs immediate attention, e.g., troubleshooting, making changes in the app, deploying enhancements, among others. She emphasized having open communication lines so everyone has a holistic view of the problem being addressed (Refer to **WL3-07** for more context.)

These women IT leaders demonstrate adaptability and situational leadership in their communicative practices. They adapt their delegation styles to individual team members' abilities and motivations, aligning their actions with the organization's evolving values and business needs. The women leaders also practice agility in their communication, balancing both technical and human aspects. They adapt their communication styles to industry shifts and situational demands, employing a range of approaches from instructional to collaborative decision-making.

Women leaders practice open and transparent communication.

Both WL1 and WL3 put a strong emphasis on utilizing communication channels to foster open communication among their teams. WL1 in particular leveraged Slack, making it easier for her team to reach her.

“Second is to communicate openly. And that's always what I've told the people at ### is our Slack is open for everybody to come to me and ask me, but I will also talk to your leader because it's a triumvirate wherein it's your leader, myself, and their team member who we're going to be talking to.” [WL1-08]

Similarly, WL3 highlighted how there exists a plethora of channels where teams can stay connected. She also emphasized going beyond transactional meetings about projects, but really take time to check in with her people.

*“I'm glad to say that nowadays, it's easier to **stay connected** because there's so **many channels**, right? What I do is I have daily check-ins. It's not necessarily a formal check-in. **It's the messages that you send in the morning, throughout the day, that you just check in with people, how they're doing, what's the update on a particular project, just so that they know that you're with them through the day, right? And I have these one-on-ones that are not a project list update. These are just 30-minute meetings.**” [WL3-09]*

In addition to open communication, WL2 highlighted trust and focusing on the work outputs rather than the hours spent by the employees.

*“So I think the trust, the communication, and just focusing on the output rather than the hours spent will really push people to work smarter. I mean, **if you want to do a home errand or a family errand, I'm okay with that for as long as you get the thing delivered on time.**” [WL2-09]*

In the same vein, WL4 emphasized the trust that people have in their leaders and that said leaders should effectively communicate with their teams, particularly when there are ongoing changes in the organization.

*“So as a leader, it's important for people in your team to **understand why there is a need to change, explain the reasons**”*

behind the change, including the issues, pain points, and the direction of the organization. So as a leader, we must give people an opportunity to ask questions and make suggestions how to go about the change. Of course, it's important to address their concerns and show people how the change benefits them personally.” [WL4-07]

These women IT leaders practice open and transparent communication. They create an environment where issues are quickly identified and resolved, visions are aligned, and support is readily available, by establishing open communication channels, maintaining consistency in interactions, and promoting transparency. They ensure responsiveness to customer inquiries, create an environment where open and honest communication is encouraged, and clearly communicate their expectations for team members. These women IT leaders use straightforward communication, including the use of visual representations, to ensure their teams understand what they mean.

Women leaders practice empathy and understanding.

The practice of empathy and understanding can be traced to the genuine care women leaders possess. WL1 mentioned taking care of oneself, setting time for oneself, not fully worrying about the future by embracing ambiguity. (Refer to **WL1-03** for more context.) Similarly, WL2 emphasized taking care of her teammates, giving needed breaks, understanding that people are not machines.

“If you think you worked so much during the weekend and you need a break, then have that break because at the end of the day, the team is not a machine. We are all individuals. We're human

*beings. We really have to take a break once in a while. Surprisingly, last year, **productivity even went up**, but in fact, no.” [WL2-10]*

WL3 on the other hand, emphasized empathy, understanding that everyone has different experiences from each other.

*“And I think **there should be respect and empathy for each individual**. I talk about empathy because nowadays that's important. Everybody's going through a particular journey and you don't see that because you don't go to the office together, right?” [WL3-10]*

Beyond experience, WL3 also highlighted how different people can bring diverse strengths and can support the team as a whole.

*“Yeah, agree. And **most of your Zoom meetings are really going through the motions**, going through all of the things you have to achieve, things you have to deliver, right? So, there needs to be that embedded empathy in each of us and an appreciation of what **each person can bring to the team and you supplement and complement those strengths** with those of the other people in the team, right?” [WL3-12]*

Likewise, empathizing with people also means understanding that there might be fear when one introduces change in the organization. With a people-focused approach, WL4 was able to communicate the changes in their organization. (Refer to excerpt **WL4-01** for more context.)

Both WL3 and WL4 emphasized positive feedback. WL4 emphasized recognizing people for their efforts.

*“While you're undergoing the change, also use **positive feedback and recognition to encourage people toward the new way.**” [WL4-08]*

While, WL3 articulated the need to celebrate small and big wins with their teams. Recognizing small wins and celebrating the big ones, to keep the team motivated.

*“And lastly, to be able to recognize the **small wins and the big wins.** It's not always perfect, you know? Like even for us running an e-commerce platform, every day is a challenge. There seems to be a war that we're fighting every day, whether it's internal or external, right? But we make it a point to **recognize those small wins and, of course, celebrate the big wins** and that matters a lot to keep the team motivated, right? So, I think those things.” [WL3-11]*

These women IT leaders demonstrate empathy and understanding in their communicative practices. They leverage the unique strengths of each team member and practice positive feedback and recognition to encourage desired behaviors. The leaders promote belonging by using inclusive language and shared values thus setting the tone for a positive and productive work environment. They also actively listen to the needs of team members, stay connected with their teams, as well as celebrate both small and big wins. The women IT leaders emphasize leading by example and encourage team cohesion, collaboration, and idea sharing, creating a supportive environment.

Women leaders practice data-driven, tech-enabled, and customer-focused communication.

WL4 emphasized proactive research and the importance of asking questions in order to elicit how fit one is in their desired organization or role.

*“Yeah, so you have to do your **research and find out more about the organization**. So I think one important aspect is culture, the culture of the organization. Culture is really about how things are done in the organization, what are the **shared beliefs and values of the leaders and the people** in the organization. Learn about the culture and **ask questions about it**. It will give you an idea if you will thrive in that work environment by knowing the culture.” [WL4-09]*

Similarly, WL1 highlighted focusing on the facts and objectively responding to the situation rather than subjectively reacting to it.

*So what I've been able to do is really keep my cool, and I **go over the facts and remove the subjectivity** and the personalities involved. Because that's where you will **react to what's happening instead of responding to it**.” [WL1-09]*

WL1 also promoted a trial-and-error approach, highlighting that whether one succeeds or fails in their business or role endeavors, the idea is to find the right solution. (Refer to **WL1-02** for more context.) In the same vein, getting first-hand data and insights from customers help leaders address their pain points which are continuously evolving and changing. (Refer to **WL3-08** for more information and context.)

Moreover, these women IT leaders emphasized the value of customer experience and satisfaction. WL2 articulated the importance of knowing customers more than the things that they can gain from the organization. (Refer to **WL2-01** for more context.) WL3

mentioned how customers don't see the complexity of operations. That's why it's important to address issues backend and on-the-ground, through data collected via the app, in order to maintain a smooth customer experience. (Refer to **WL3-05** for more context.) Similarly, WL4 noted how technology can be used to improve employee experiences by reducing manual processes which in turn improves customer experiences. (Refer to **WL4-06** for more context.) WL2 saw the need to create solutions that address and anticipate customer needs. (Refer to **WL2-07** for more context.)

The communicative practices of women IT leaders highlight data-driven, tech-enabled, and customer-focused communication. They emphasize responsiveness, focusing on objective facts, leveraging data, and promoting shared goals, in order to encourage problem-solving and customer-centricity. To enhance work processes and contribute to societal development, these women leaders promote the use of technology. They also utilize storytelling techniques as well as virtual communication channels to effectively convey their message and engage with their team and customers. The leaders proactively identify and address issues, actively listen to customer feedback to anticipate their needs and break down complex processes into simpler components.

Synthesis of the Communicative Practices of Women Leaders

To explore the communicative practices of the women IT leaders, codes were identified and assigned as communicative practices. The table below summarizes these insights.

Table 4. Summary of Communicative Practices of Women IT Leaders

Women leaders practice continuous learning and self-improvement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Admitting what you don't know • Being open to changes and learning new things • Continuously developing new skills
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<p>Women leaders practice adaptability and situational leadership.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leaders emphasize continuous learning and self-improvement • Leaders encourage having goals for the future • Leaders encourage proactiveness and note the danger of being stagnant • Leaders learn the facts by asking questions • Leaders practice proactive background research • Leaders adapt their delegation style based on the team members' knowledge, skills, and motivations • Leaders leverage organizational values to align the team's actions with the evolving business needs • Leaders practice agility in the way they communicate • Leaders practice change communication, balancing both the technical and people aspects of the change • Leaders shift the way they communicate in response to the changes in the industry • Leaders shift their communicative practices based on the situation • Leaders use a range of styles from instructional to collaborative decision-making
<p>Women leaders practice open and transparent communication.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leaders communicate clearly what values they look for from their team • Leaders emphasize responsiveness by staying connected to customer-accessed channels • Leaders encourage open communication, allowing team members to share their thoughts and ideas • Leaders encourage transparent communication • Leaders establish open communication channels • Leaders leverage consistency in interactions to encourage desired behavior • Leaders leverage open communication, ensuring that issues are quickly identified and resolved • Leaders make sure that visions are aligned • Leaders practice clear communication by being straightforward • Leaders practice open communication • Leaders promote transparent communication as they create a transparent environment • Leaders promote transparent communication, addressing concerns and providing needed support • Leaders use visualization of operations to communicate their points clearly
<p>Women leaders practice empathy and understanding.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leaders actively listen to the needs of their employees • Leaders emphasize celebrating small and big wins • Leaders emphasize celebrating small and big wins • Leaders emphasize staying connected with their team • Leaders emphasize the importance of leading by example or "walking the talk" • Leaders encourage team cohesion and collaboration • Leaders encourage team members to share ideas and feedback • Leaders leverage the different strengths of team members • Leaders make use of different communication channels to reach their team • Leaders practice behavior change communication, focusing on influencing change in mindsets • Leaders practice positive feedback and recognition to encourage desired behavior • Leaders practice positive feedback and recognition to encourage desired behavior • Leaders promote belonging by using inclusive language • Leaders promote empathy and understanding • Leaders promote proactiveness and note the danger of being stagnant • Leaders promote shared values among their team • Leaders set the tone of the day through communication • Leaders stay in touch by remaining actively involved in projects and meetings • Leaders use personal narratives to relate with their team and communicate their point across • Success requires empathy and understanding
<p>Women leaders practice data-driven, tech-enhanced, and customer-focused communication.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being solution-oriented by proactively identifying and addressing issues • Leaders actively listen to the "voice of the customer" to anticipate their needs • Leaders actively listen to the needs and concerns of their customers

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- Leaders actively listen to the needs of the customers, anticipating their implicit and explicit needs
 - Leaders break down complex processes to simpler components
 - Leaders emphasize responsiveness by staying connected to customer-accessed channels
 - Leaders focus on objective facts and removing subjectivity
 - Leaders leverage data in solving problems
 - Leaders practice proactive background research
 - Leaders promote a shared goal of addressing customer needs
 - Leaders promote the use of technology as a tool to enhance work processes
 - Leaders promote using tech not only for internal but also for societal development
 - Leaders use narratives similar to the value that they would to communicate
 - Leaders use personal narratives to communicate their point across
 - Leaders use personal stories to get their point across
 - Leaders utilize virtual communication channels in operations
 - Promoting technology as a tool to enhance work processes and societal development
 - Utilizing virtual communication channels in operations
-

To address the second research question— what are the communicative practices of women IT leaders —five key themes have emerged:

1. Women leaders practice continuous learning and self-improvement.
2. Women leaders practice adaptability and situational leadership.
3. Women leaders practice open and transparent communication.
4. Women leaders practice empathy and understanding.
5. Women leaders practice data-driven, tech-enhanced, and customer-focused communication.

Accomplishments of the Communicative Practices in Leadership

Based on the findings in this study, the communicative practices of women IT leaders help accomplish company stability, sustainability, competitiveness, relevance, improved team collaboration and engagement, as well as adaptability and innovation. These accomplishments are detailed below.

Keeping the company stable and sustainable

The communicative practices of women IT leaders help them achieve company stability and sustainability by ensuring sustainable growth, keeping relevance in a changing landscape, and maintaining operational continuity even in remote work environments.

In particular, the communicative practice highlighting data-driven, tech-enhanced, and customer-focused communication helps achieve stability. By emphasizing proactive problem-solving, making decisions based on data, actively listening to customer needs, simplifying complex processes, and leveraging tech for communication to maintain efficiency all help drive the company forward. Refer to excerpts **WL1-07**, **WL2-04**, **WL2-08**, **WL3-03**, and **WL4-02** for more context.

Keeping the company competitive and relevant

The communicative practices of women IT leaders help accomplish organizational competitiveness and relevance by ensuring adaptability to changes, maintaining a competitive edge, fostering innovation and growth, and staying relevant in the rapidly evolving industry.

By practicing adaptability and situational leadership, these women leaders keep their companies competitive and relevant. Being agile in the way they communicate, adjusting based on the trends in the industry, and managing tech and people aspects through effective change communication, all help these women leaders stay ahead of the curve. Refer to **WL1-04**, **WL2-05**, **WL3-07**, and **WL4-01** for more context.

Improving team collaboration and engagement

The communicative practices of women IT leaders help them to accomplish improved team performance, collaboration, engagement, and satisfaction. Particularly, employing open and transparent communication as well as empathy and understanding helps improve team collaboration and engagement among their teams. Encouraging their teams to voice out ideas, promoting a sense of belonging, and providing clear feedback foster trust and encourage collective problem-solving. For more context, please refer to excerpts **WL1-08**, **WL3-09**, **WL2-09**, and **WL4-07**.

In line with that, actively listening to employee needs, celebrating wins, leading by example, and leveraging individual strengths help women leaders build stronger relationships among their team members. For this particular insight, please refer to excerpts **WL1-03**, **WL2-10**, **WL3-10**, **WL4-01**, **WL4-08**, and **WL3-11** for more context. Their communicative practices foster a cohesive work culture, enhance team morale, and create a more engaged workforce. By leveraging individual strengths and promoting effective collaboration, women leaders improve team performance, employee engagement, and job satisfaction.

Enabling and promoting adaptability and innovation

The communicative practices of women IT leaders help them achieve adaptability and innovation. Practicing continuous learning and self-improvement supports these women leaders' endeavors in creating a culture of innovation among their teams. From changing or adjusting their communication styles based on the demands of the situation to aligning team efforts to evolving business needs, these women leaders promote

innovation and adaptability. Refer to excerpts **WL1-02, WL1-09, WL2-01, WL2-07, WL3-05, WL3-08, WL3-12, WL4-06,** and **WL4-09** for better context.

By fostering clear decision-making, effective problem-solving, creating an agile workforce, maintaining adaptability to change, and successfully implementing organizational changes, the communicative practices of women leaders can also contribute to nation-building and development.

Synthesis of the Accomplishment in Leadership of the Women IT Leaders’ Communicative Practices

To understand the accomplishment in leadership of the women IT leaders’ communicative practices, codes were identified and assigned as accomplishment in leadership. The table below summarizes these insights.

Table 5. Summary of the Accomplishment in Leadership of the Women IT Leaders’ Communicative Practices

Keeping the company stable and sustainable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keeping the company stable • Keeping the company stable and its growth sustainable • Keeping the company stable and relevant • Keeping the company sustainable • Keeping the company operational despite the remote work setup
Keeping the company competitive and relevant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keeping the company adaptable and relevant • Keeping the company competitive • Keeping the company competitive and relevant • Keeping the company competitive through innovation and growth • Keeping the company relevant • Keeping the company relevant amidst changes • Keeping the company relevant by swiftly adapting to shifts and changes • Keeping the company relevant in fast-evolving industry • Keeping the company relevant in the fast-changing industry
Improving team collaboration and engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better company performance • Building the team morale • Creates a more engaged workforce • Enable team members to perform effectively • Foster cohesive work culture and shared values among team members • Fostering collaboration and strong team dynamics • Increased commitment and job satisfaction • Optimized team performance by leveraging individual strengths • Promoting better team collaboration • Promoting healthy collaboration and strong team dynamics • Promoting higher engagement among team members

Enabling and promoting adaptability and innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustaining effective leadership and resilience • Clear decision-making and effective problem-solving • Contribute to nation-building and development • Creating an agile workforce • Keeping the company adaptable to uncertain changes • Keeping the company open and not resistant to change • Successfully implement changes in the organization
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To address the third research question— what do the communicative practices accomplish in leadership —four key themes have emerged:

1. Keeping the company stable and sustainable
2. Keeping the company competitive and relevant
3. Improving team collaboration and engagement
4. Enabling and promoting adaptability and innovation

Contribution and Relationship to Existing Knowledge

The findings of this study contributed to the existing body of knowledge, reinforcing and extending previous research. The following section aligns the results of the study in the context of the literature reviewed, highlighting both the empirical and theoretical plausibility of the findings. Comparing the study’s results with real-world applications and existing literature allows meaningful contributions to the area of study.

Views of Women IT Leaders

These women IT leaders see the industry as a continuously changing, evolving, and disruptive sector. Zooming out to real-world trends, we can see how this view resonates with other women leaders. Take for example KonsultaMD, which was originally solely a teleconsultation application. When a new female CEO took over, they began shifting from a business-to-consumer (B2C) model to a business-to-business (B2B)

approach to address the evolving needs in the market (Vicencio, 2024). This view also resonates with the points of Akbari and Pratomo (2021) who noted how, "technology has altered communication styles in modern organizations, and leaders need to adapt to these changes to be effective." Similarly, this view also reflected the need for developing new competencies in the digital age, such as digital literacy, innovative thinking, and strategic thinking (Alam et al., 2022; Baroudi, 2022; Huynh, 2020). Moreover, the changing ways of working necessitated new leadership approaches, including better collaboration skills, particularly when managing remote teams (Malek & Jaguli, 2018).

The need for flexibility, adaptability, and agility are also underscored by these women IT leaders. From the researcher's experience working in a fintech for transport, it was observed how women leaders tend to be adaptable. For example, their chief operating officer that time was also double-hatting as the chief marketing officer. This just goes to show how women can be adaptable depending on the needs of the business. This is also reflected in existing literature just as stated by Baroudi (2022), "leaders must be flexible, proactive and good communicators, so they convey the changes and goals clearly and effectively to their staff" and Huynh (2020), "As part of professional growth, the women practiced self-care and showed a great level of flexibility, allowing themselves to take risks, follow their intuition, and make mistakes." Same with the observations of Akbari and Pratomo (2021) who noted that technology changed the way organizations operate highlighting how "leaders need to adapt to these changes to be effective."

Women IT leaders also view success as defined by resilience and problem-solving. This is similar to the trends that we see globally and are highlighted by Mariappan (2021) who noted in an article that, "managing ambiguity, maintaining resilience, and

demonstrating emotional intelligence” are some of the capabilities women bring to their leadership. This view reinforced existing literature which documented traits of Filipina leaders— resilience, empathy, strong leadership skills, and a determined personality (Alberto, 2023; Dasig, 2020; Osi & Teng-Calleja, 2021). These qualities, shaped by their cultural background, contribute to the Filipina women leaders’ leadership and communicative practices, making them particularly successful in their field.

These women IT leaders view the industry as a diverse and highly collaborative sector. Likewise, this too aligns with the trends we can observe in other countries, particularly the United States, where Tia Gordon, former VP of People & Culture at Getaround, said in an article written by Beales (2023) that, “we will continue to see a shift towards the normalization of women and minorities in leadership roles and, with this shift, we will also begin to see higher collaboration across industry lines.” This view resonated with the unique perspective of women leaders identified by Malek & Jaguli (2018), which stated that collective action is necessary for societal success therefore requiring a collaborative decision-making approach.

Finally, these women IT leaders also view customer-centricity and satisfaction as important factors in the industry. Similarly, it reflects industry trends as demonstrated by Kavitha Mariappan the EVP for Customer Experience and Transformation of Zscaler who stated that, “When it comes to business outcomes, she sees the hierarchy of priorities as putting the customer first, followed by the company and oneself (Mariappan, 2021).” This shows that customers are an essential part of a successful business, and women leaders in IT are leading the way in this approach. This advanced existing research by showing how their views are influenced by the societal context in which they operate. The

customer-focused nature of IT shaped their communicative practices. As Biddix (2010) noted, societal structures influence women's leadership behaviors, making effective communicative practices invaluable vehicle for leadership.

Communicative Practices of Women IT Leaders

These women IT leaders practiced continuous learning and self-improvement. In the researcher's recent organization, employees are always encouraged to pursue learning using online platforms. The organization is also providing free access to these learning tools, democratizing opportunities for growth and development. This practice reinforced the existing literature, as Thompson (2021) noted in an article: "Improvements we make today will have an outsized effect on the workplace tomorrow—not just for women, but for the entire working world." Similarly, it underscored the importance of digital literacy, innovative and strategic thinking, and enhanced collaboration skills, particularly in leading virtual and remote teams (Alam et al., 2022; Huynh, 2020; Malek & Jaguli, 2018). Likewise, it supports existing literature, as noted in a study by Baroudi (2022) stating that "being a lifelong learner, being always open for development and learning about the new changes is a fundamental leadership characteristic." Moreover, studies stress the need for companies to invest in digital skills development, especially for women in leadership roles, and the critical need for digital and transformational leadership during crises (Fransson & Frisk, 2021; Dasig, 2020). The study contributed to these findings by examining how women leaders practiced continuous learning and self-improvement in order to succeed in their fields.

Adaptability and situational leadership are also practiced by women IT leaders. As observed by the researcher, women leaders are proficient in navigating evolving market dynamics. This includes exploring new markets to address local challenges, setting their sight to other regions, and proactively leveraging new and emerging opportunities. This aligns with insights from existing literature as well. Particularly the notions from the *Women's Leadership in the Digital Era: Agility, Adaptability and Fluency (2022)*, which highlighted the importance of digital leadership among women during the pandemic, which required them to be agile and adept at adapting to new norms. This echoes the findings of Baroudi (2022), which highlighted the effective leadership qualities employed by Arab female educational leaders during crises, including flexibility, proactiveness, and a service-oriented approach, which are important attributes for success.

These women IT leaders practiced open and transparent communication. Looking at broader industry trends, we can see the increasing importance the practice is gaining in the field. Insight from these trends stress the impact of open and transparent communication in creating safe spaces and promoting inclusion (Larsen, 2021; Mariappan, 2021). This also aligns with insights from existing literature, just as Jad-Moussa (2022) noted, recognizing individual and collective accomplishments contributes to transparency, and leaders who work alongside and support their staff foster engagement, motivation, transparency, and trust. This study contributed to the literature by showing how women leaders employ communicative practices, such as openness, to address challenges like gender bias, the "glass ceiling," and the digital divide (Hejase et al., 2013; Alam et al., 2022).

Empathy and understanding are also considered crucial practices of women IT leaders. Going to real-world trends, an online article from Beales (2023) emphasized the growing importance of empathy, resiliency, and representation in the workplace, especially in the post-pandemic era. People-centric approaches to leadership, recognizing the value of empathy, self-care, and work-life balance were greatly emphasized. In the same vein, Oppenauer (2021) underscored the impact of communication, empathy, and collaboration skills in effective leadership. These align with insights from existing literature, just as Huynh (2020) highlighted the importance of self-care, flexibility, risk-taking, and building trusting partnerships based on empathy and collaboration among women leaders. Similarly, it aligns with existing literature on the leadership traits of Filipina leaders, highlighting the importance of resilience and empathy (Alberto, 2023; Dasig, 2020; Osi & Teng-Calleja, 2021). These perspectives collectively highlight the importance of empathy and understanding as key qualities for leaders in today's evolving workplace.

Finally, women leaders also practiced data-driven, tech-enhanced, and customer-focused communication. This resonates with recent trends, as highlighted by Elisabeth Oppenauer, Learning & Development Consultant from MDI Management Development International, who found that women are well-prepared for a digital future since they are comfortable with new technologies, trust data, and are open to innovative collaborations (Oppenauer, 2021). Similarly, Mariappan (2021) noted how women leaders emphasized the importance of prioritizing customers, then the company, before themselves. This contributed to the existing literature by indicating how such practices help women IT leaders navigate the industry effectively. Technology enabled women in leadership roles

by offering new opportunities to assert their leadership (Huynh, 2020). In addition to that, Moreno-Gómez et al. (2018) emphasized how women leaders' communicative practices have been linked to improved business outcomes stating that diverse leadership can lead to "more revenue, customers, market share, and profits."

Accomplishments of the Communicative Practices in Leadership

The communicative practices of women IT leaders help keep the company stable and sustainable. This resonates with the researcher's experiences where women leaders in their organization regularly conduct company-wide events where the leaders communicate the status and financial standing of the company, promoting transparency and stability. Similarly, broader trends as noted by Oppenauer (2020) emphasized that in today's digital, technological, and VUCA-driven world, leaders require new skills to achieve sustainable success. Ignoring the influence and skills of female employees is not an option for companies aiming to thrive in the industry. This finding is reflected in existing literature as highlighted by Alam et al. (2022), who found that the use of tech resources and capabilities—such as social networks, workplace culture, innovation, internationalization, and ICT—significantly contribute to sustainable digital transformation. While, Alam et al. (2022), noted how the fresh perspectives and great consideration of more ethical and sustainable practices of women leaders help push digital transformation in their respective sectors. Particular to the Philippine context, finding from Philippine Business Coalition for Women Empowerment & Philippine Women's Economic Network assert that having better financial and business outcomes is linked to having women in leadership positions (PBCWE & PhilWEN, 2019).

Another accomplishment of women leaders' communicative practices is keeping companies competitive and relevant. Specifically, one of the women IT leaders in this study, demonstrated this by successfully shifting their company's business model to meet evolving market demands. This is reflected in existing literature, particularly the studies from Chuang & Eversole (2022) and Umar (2021), which underscored the important contributions of women IT leaders to organizational success. Women's unique qualities foster positive work environments, innovation, and overall organizational competitiveness. This highlights the importance of having women leaders in maintaining organizational competitiveness and relevance in the rapidly evolving tech landscape. This resonates with the findings of Moreno-Gómez, et al. (2018) who observed how companies with more diverse board and management teams tended to perform better.

Women leaders also improve team collaboration and engagement through their communicative practices. This aligns with the insights from recent trends, such as the emphasis on the importance of communication, empathy, and collaboration skills which positions women to be "well prepared for a digital future" (Oppenauer, 2021). Likewise, this also aligns with existing literature, in the studies from Jad-Moussa (2022) and Huynh (2020), which highlighted the importance of leaders who actively support their staff and foster a supportive, empowering environment. By emphasizing collaboration, authenticity, and empathy, women leaders create high-performing teams and contribute to positive company growth and success. Similarly, it reflects the need for improved collaboration skills, particularly when leading virtual teams, as noted by Malek & Jaguli (2018).

Finally, women leaders' communicative practices enable and promote adaptability and innovation. Particular to this study, one women IT leader leveraged technology and data in order to cope up with evolving customer needs, highlighting how innovation is necessary in order to adapt to market changes, Similarly, Oppenauer (2021) highlighted how women are well-prepared for the digital future. Their strong communication and networking skills, combined with a comfort level with new technologies and a trust in data analysis, position them as effective leaders in driving innovation and adapting to change. Likewise, Mariappan (2021) noted that "diverse companies outperform their less diverse peers in innovation, problem-solving, and agility," underscoring the value of diverse leadership. This finding also aligns with existing literature, as Malek and Jaguli (2018) found in their study, key traits of effective female leadership (including an open and informal approach to power, fostering creativity and innovation, and managing diversity effectively) are important in order to navigate the complexities of IT and adapting to changing circumstances. Similarly, Filipina business executives demonstrated flexibility and multitasking skills, essential for overcoming prejudice and promoting cultures of equal opportunity (Osi & Teng-Calleja, 2021). Baroudi (2022) also highlighted how Arab female educational leaders excel during crises by exhibiting flexibility, proactiveness, and service orientation—traits crucial in digital transformation.

Podcasts as a Communication Medium

By using podcasts as the primary source of data, this study highlighted its value in leadership, gender, and communication research. Focusing on the methodology, the results of this study demonstrated how podcasts can capture the views, communicative practices, and accomplishments of women IT leaders, opening up new avenues for leadership studies.

For real world applications, podcasts during the pandemic, have become a popular medium, offering wide access to the experiences of influential individuals like business leaders. This has allowed listeners to gain valuable insights from the leaders' personal journeys and lessons in leadership.

Zooming on existing literature, this reinforces Taylor & Blevins (2019) which emphasized how using podcasts as instructional tools makes them a valuable resource for investigating leadership communication.

Synthesis of the Views, Communicative Practices, and Accomplishments in Leadership of Women IT Leaders

To understand the views, communicative practices, and leadership accomplishments of women IT leaders, key themes were identified and examined through an ethnomethodological lens. The table below provides a summary of these insights.

Table 6. Summary of Views, Communicative Practices, and Accomplishment in Leadership of IT Leaders

Views of Women IT Leaders	Communicative Practices of Women IT Leaders	Accomplishments in Leadership
The industry is continuously changing, evolving, and is disruptive	Women leaders practice continuous learning and self-improvement	Keeping the company stable and sustainable
The industry requires flexibility, adaptability, and agility	Women leaders practice adaptability and situational leadership	Keeping the company competitive and relevant
Success is defined by resilience and problem-solving	Women leaders practice open and transparent communication	Improving team collaboration and engagement
The industry is diverse and highly collaborative	Women leaders practice empathy and understanding	Enabling and promoting adaptability and innovation
Customer-centricity and satisfaction is important in IT	Women leaders practice data-driven, tech-enhanced, and customer-focused communication	

Chapter VI

RESEARCH SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary

The study sought to explore the communicative practices of women IT leaders through narratives present in podcast conversations. This aims to peruse the nuanced communicative practices employed by women IT leaders, while also studying how their views inform these practices and what these practices accomplish in their leadership roles. Based on the Sociocultural Tradition of Communication, where Craig (1999) proposed that communication is “a symbolic process that produces and reproduces shared sociocultural patterns,” the researcher used ethnomethodology to analyze the narratives from four (4) podcast episodes featuring women IT leaders in the industry including a Chief Executive Officer of an advertising tech firm, a Vice President for Employee Experience of a telecom provider, a Chief Executive Officer of a digital grocery app, and an Executive Vice President of a digital banking company. These episodes were selected for the rich context they offer on the women leaders’ communicative practices. The data were collected via transcription of the podcast conversations and subjected to an ethnomethodological analysis to make sense of how the women IT leaders’ views inform their communicative practices and what they accomplish in their leadership positions through said practices. Initial codes were assigned from the podcast conversations, which were then subjected into a thematic analysis to establish the views, communicative practices, and accomplishments of women IT leaders.

The findings of the study defined five (5) views of women IT leaders: the industry is continuously changing, evolving, and disruptive; the industry requires flexibility, adaptability, and agility; success is defined by resilience and problem-solving; the industry is diverse and highly collaborative; and customer-centricity and satisfaction is important in IT. In line with that, the findings of the study also described five (5) communicative practices namely: women leaders practice continuous learning and self-improvement; women leaders practice adaptability and situational leadership; women leaders practice open and transparent communication; women leaders practice empathy and understanding; and women leaders practice data-driven, tech-enhanced, and customer-focused communication. Finally, the findings of the study also indicated four (4) accomplishments in leadership which are as follows: keeping the company stable and sustainable; keeping the company competitive and relevant; improving team collaboration and engagement; and enabling and promoting adaptability and innovation.

Conclusion

With the findings of the study restated previously, we can therefore conclude that it has achieved its purpose of exploring the communicative practices employed by women IT leaders, while also exploring how their views of the sector inform their practices and what these practices accomplish in their leadership roles. Viewing this through an ethnomethodological lens allowed us to better understand the interaction between language, gender, and leadership by analyzing how women IT leaders use communication to navigate their unique roles.

The study revealed that the views of these women leaders are not universal truths but are shaped by their roles in the industry. For example, the view that the industry is continuously changing, evolving, and disruptive is influenced by WL1's role as the CEO of an advertising tech firm, highlighting how the shift from traditional aggregation models to direct sales demands that her company stay ahead of the curve. In contrast, WL2's perspective is shaped by her role as the VP for Employee Experience at a telecom provider, underscoring how the challenges brought on by the pandemic necessitated rapid technological adaptation to maintain employee engagement and service delivery.

We can also conclude that the communicative practices employed by women IT leaders both shape and are shaped by their views on the industry. For example, women leaders practice adaptability and situational leadership because they recognize the need for flexibility, adaptability, and agility in IT. Similarly, women leaders practice data-driven, tech-enhanced, and customer-focused communication, as they view customer-centricity and satisfaction as crucial factors in IT.

Moreover, examining what these communicative practices accomplish in the leadership roles of these women revealed how these accomplishments are deeply connected to how they make their communicative practices accountable to their teams, organizations, and the broader industry. For example, improving team collaboration and engagement is one of the goals that women leaders achieve through their communicative practices. In particular, women leaders practice open and transparent communication, as well as empathy and understanding, to create an inclusive environment where team members feel valued and motivated to contribute, leading to better collaboration and higher levels of engagement.

Finally, the findings of this study respond to the call for a deeper understanding of women leaders' unique perspectives and approaches to different opportunities and challenges. By categorizing their views, the study sheds light on how these leaders view and approach the dynamic environment of the IT sector. Their communicative practices are crucial for understanding how women leaders effectively manage their teams and organizations in a rapidly evolving industry.

Recommendation

The findings of this study, established the views, communicative practices, and accomplishments of women IT leaders. Recognizing the need for further research in this area of study, the following suggestions are recommended:

Theoretical

Future research on the women leaders' communicative practices can utilize a phenomenological lens in order to further more deeply explore the lived experiences of women IT leaders. This can provide richer context into how these women leaders perceive and interpret the challenges they face, the communicative practices they employ, and how being women information technology leaders influence their leadership and communication styles.

Methodological

To further assess if the findings of this study apply to the general population of women leaders, future research may incorporate quantitative or mixed-method approaches. Utilizing structured questionnaires and surveys distributed to a larger population of women information technology leaders would allow validation of the communicative practices identified in the study and see how much of it are applied by other women leaders in the sector.

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